

ORION | Trapezium

**Work and Imaging Records for the Meade LX200
2024-2025**

**Reprinted from Trapezium Issues
Aug, Sep, Oct, Nov, Dec 2024;
Mar, Apr, Jun 2025**

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Aug 2024 Trapezium
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ORION and TAO Last Month/ 10 Aug 2024:

Meade Enhancement and Perseid Meteor Watch

Prelude: Messing with the Meade

Rob Fowler and I arrived in the late afternoon of 10 Aug because we wanted to get started on an attempt to use the somewhat vintage 12" LX200 Meade (now in the glow dome) for astrophotography. In view of the large aperture and the stability of the pier mount, this might prove to be a useful instrument.

The two largely separate aspects of this development are 1) attaching and operating a modern cpu-controlled camera, perhaps using the very popular astrocamera controller program "SharpCap," and 2) updating the Celestron CGE mount by replacing the old hand controller by a connection to a modern mount control program such as Celestron - Plane Wave International's collaborative "CPWI" program. (Both programs are available as free downloads, and the upgraded version of SharpCap is only a modest expense.)

Since this mount predates the now ubiquitous USB connections, the step of introducing the telescope's optical tube assembly "OTA" to a modern astrocamera had seemed like the easier place to start. Daytime was needed because one can use bright nearby scenes and then distant ones to confirm that the camera is imaging correctly, and is in good focus. Save the faint objects for later.

Using my ZWOASI294MC-Pro cooled color camera, Rob attached it to the Meade, and I connected its USB 3.0 output to my Win 10 Pro cpu, which has SharpCap installed, and is my standard cpu for running astrophotography software. I also connected the camera sensor cooling power supply. Sighting the Meade across the TAO grounds to the North, with coarse and then fine focus, we eventually captured a "first astrophotographic light" image for this Meade-ZWO combination. An initial uncertainty was finding a suitable daytime exposure and gain for single images; I settled on RGB24, gain 130 (570 is max), and an exposure of 4 msec. The "first light" astroimage that I captured is shown on the following page.

ORION and TAO Last Month/ 10 Aug 2024: Meade Enhancement

An out of focus image of leaves in the top of a tree (Fr. *arbre*) may be a standard “first light” image in astrophotography.

The “first light” image from the 12” LX200 Meade with the ZWO camera at TAO. The time recorded by the cpu camera (timestamp on the frame) was 5:22:19 pm Eastern, 10 Aug 2024.

The sharpness of the twig’s image at a distance of *ca.* 100 m is reassuring; if the thin stem has a diameter of 2 mm, the width of the stem image is about 4 arcseconds, reasonably good for a first image. Other parts of the image being out of focus might indicate a very short depth of field, or more likely fast motion on a windy day.

After a few more exciting leaf shots we moved to the only accessible distant horizon, to the West, but as the Sun was growing lower in the West, those images were washed out and hard to interpret.

ORION and TAO Last Month/ 10 Aug 2024: Meade Enhancement

Rob Fowler selecting potential targets for the 12" Meade to the Northeast. 5:45 pm Eastern.

Setting up my cpu and ZWO ASI294MC-Pro camera (red cylinder) to work with the Meade telescope. 6:50 pm Eastern.

ORION and TAO Last Month/ 10 Aug 2024: Meade Enhancement

As the Moon was high in the sky, Rob suggested we try it next. This worked reasonably well (after considerable searching for the moon), however Perseid-seeking visitors started arriving, so we spent time welcoming them and showing them around. From about 8 pm we again had some free time, and after some changes of gain and exposure (to 2 ms and a gain of about 300) and careful focus adjustment, this result followed.

A lunar image using the 12" Meade at TAO. The timestamp recorded 8:46:41 pm Eastern, 10 Aug 2024. At this time the Moon was in Virgo, Alt@Azi = 27.5 deg @ 223.8 deg, just above TAO's highest treetops to the Southwest.

ORION and TAO Last Month/ 10 Aug 2024: Meade Enhancement

Clearly our “first light” day for the venerable Meade would be incomplete without capturing an image of something outside the solar system. There were thin clouds in the sky that precluded some obvious choices. A few images of Deneb taken about 10:30 pm Eastern were not pleasing, in part because the roof of the “igloo” was occluding some of the field of view (Alt 60 deg), and at 8sG570, many star images were showing some coma.

Rob suggested moving to an object in Sagittarius he had seen a few days previously in the Meade, the “Herschel Cluster.” This proved to be a part of M8, the Lagoon Nebula. As SharpCap was unable to align frames of this object for stacking, I was restricted to single exposures. An early attempt is shown below; one can see some hints of nebulosity.

M8, the Lagoon Nebula in Sagittarius, as seen by the 12” Meade.
This is a single 8sG520 frame, with modest post processing.

ORION and TAO Last Month/ 10 Aug 2024: Meade Enhancement

Attempts to bring out the nebulosity in M8 through longer exposures resulted in significant star trailing. A compromise 15 sec single exposure at the same gain, with post processing, is shown below.

M8, the Lagoon Nebula in Sagittarius. A single 15sG520 frame, with post processing. TAO, 10:52 pm Eastern, 10 Aug 2024. f.o.v. 22'x15'.
305 cm LX200 Meade with ZWO ASI294MC-Pro.
RA 18h 04m, Dec -24d 25m.

Sep 2024 Trapezium
pp. 23-53

Meadeian Developments:

Continued work on the TAO Meade LX200

22 Aug 2024

As described in last month's Trapezium, several people in ORION (notably moi (tb), David Fields, Rob Fowler and Noah Frere) have been entertaining a fantasy of using the venerable 12" Meade LX200 housed in the glow-dome for astrophotography. A notable possibility was to use this instrument for observing asteroid occultations, since this application would benefit from a large aperture telescope that can capture faint target stars in short exposures. Some of this Meade upgrade effort was described in last month's Trapezium, which showed our first images taken with a ZWO ASI294 MCP cooled color camera attached to the Meade, on 10 Aug 2024. Images of the Moon and the Lagoon Nebula were shown.

When considering using the Meade for astrophotography, I recalled that one important step I had done earlier with my CGX mount was to learn how to move beyond a hand controller (HC) and use the Celestron – Plane Wave International program CPWI to control the mount. A difference is that this mount is a vintage CGE.

One should do background research before jumping into a new project. In amateur astronomy we are fortunate to have the online "Cloudy Nights" site to ask for advice and assistance from others who may have experience with one's current difficulties. So, on 22 Aug under "Mounts" I posted the topic "**How to control a CGE mount with CPWI on a Windows cpu?**" which asked if anyone had experience with adapting a CGE to run under CPWI. My query reads:

"I am considering trying to run a venerable CGE mount (without the original hand controller) using the latest version of CPWI (2.5.6). The CGE mount does not have USB connections, instead there are several sockets for rj-11 [actually rj-12] and one [actually two] for rj-45. (This is assuming I recall and was told correctly; the CGE is at a site 40 miles distant, and I will need to recheck.)

Meade Work at TAO: 22 Aug 2024

“My question is what type of cable should I use to connect the mount to my cpu (where CPWI resides), and to which rj socket on the mount do I connect? The cpu is a more recent Win 10 Pro, with mainly USB connections (and HDMI), and a single rj-45 (Ethernet?) and 15-pin (monitor?) socket. I have found and purchased an rj-45 to USB cable, which claims to be Celestron relevant, and a direct rj-11 - USB adapter, assuming those might prove useful.

“Any relevant shared experiences and suggestions would be appreciated. Thanks!”

The three responses I received on Cloudy Nights follow.

1) WadeH237:

“The CGE with the original controller has a modular RJ-11 serial port on the bottom of the hand controller. If the original controller has been replaced with a NexStar+ controller, it will have a micro USB connector on the bottom of the hand controller instead of the RJ-11.

There is an RJ-45 port on the electronics pier that is labeled "PC Port". Contrary to popular belief, that is not an abbreviation for "Personal Computer Port". It is short for "Programming Cable Port". To that end, it does require a special cable that is not a standard serial configuration. Here is a link to the correct part on the B&H web site. [Ed.: They list it, Celestron part 93922, as no longer available.] I could not find it on the Celestron web site, and it looks like it's been discontinued. And here is a link to the pinout and general instructions for making up your own cable.

[Ed.: <https://www.nexstarsite.com/PCControl/ProgrammingCable.htm>]

Unfortunately, I can't answer any software questions, since I upgraded from my CGE before CPWI was released. The issue is that not all of the "smarts" of a CGE are in the electronics pier. The mount is dependent on the hand controller for most of its functionality. Back in the day, I used a hand control emulator called NexRemote. It was basically a full featured hand controller implemented in software that worked with a computer connected to the PC Port on the electronics pier.

Meade Work at TAO: 22 Aug 2024

1) WadeH237 (cont.):

If CPWI has sufficient functionality to initialize and align the mount, then it may work fine without the hand controller. If not, you will need to use the physical hand controller to set up the mount. After it's aligned, you can use CPWI with an RJ-11 serial cable plugged into the bottom of the hand controller.

I hope that this helps,
-Wade”

[Ed.: Although a direct serial-to-serial mount to CPU connection sounds attractive, the web site referenced above states that “The two uses of this connection would be to run NexRemote without the use of the real hand control and to update the motor control firmware in the mount.” The site itself makes no mention of running CPWI.]

2) nic35:

“If you have some limited soldering skills, you can build your own interface box. There a very long topic in the Celestron computerized telescope forum that discusses this project. See [<https://www.cloudynights.com/topic/854327-homebrew-gen3-pcb-wifibtgpsmus-brelay/>] An easier to read and follow set of instructions can be found here <https://rtr.ca/hbg3/>

It's a pretty easy to build device.

You don't need to add all the bells and whistles. For example, I didn't install the switches - I use jumpers when I want to change the switch settings, which is very infrequent.

If all you want to do is run cpwi, you need nothing beyond the basic board. No need for GPS, nunchuck, dew controllers, oled display, etc,

I may have an extra functioning version floating around, if you are interested - for the cost of postage. I'll look and PM you.

Meade Work at TAO: 22 Aug 2024

2) nic35 (cont.):

I used an earlier version of this to control my CGEM. I connected the device to the mount and to my on-mount PC (intel NUC) and remoted into that via a dedicated wifi network. Works flawlessly.

john”

[Ed.: This use of a simple interface box sounded very attractive, especially in that John Gall later emailed to say that he had found one of these, and would send it to me, free of charge.]

3) calypsob: (26 Aug)

“I have a cge. I bought a new nexstar controller with usb integrated into the hc, you need a usb ground loop isolator between the pc and nexstar remote. CpwI connects with ease, and works very well.

-Wes”

This also sounded promising, I replied to Wes on 30 Aug asking about vendors, part numbers, and more information regarding the ground loop isolator.

In the interim, our next trip to TAO to work on the Meade was 26 Aug, as described below.

ORION Board Meeting : Mon 26 Aug 2024

Typically at 1 pm on Mondays we have a quasi-official ORION Board Meeting, which is occasionally sufficiently official to vote on matters relevant to ORION and TAO, but is more often an excuse to have a nice Mexican lunch at El Cantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge, and to discuss matters astronomical. Attendance is by no means limited to Board Members, but an interest in astronomy is encouraged.

On 26 Aug our meeting was attended by David Fields, Juan Carbajo, Art Allison, Rob Fowler, and Ted Barnes (myself). We did manage to confirm Rob in the role of Secretary by unanimous vote, since Noah Frere was no longer interested in this position. We discussed a few matters such as the next speaker, making arrangements for speaker publicity, and future activities at TAO, such as the possibility of observing an occultation on Sat 31 Aug. This would be at 10:22 pm, and would involve the asteroid 5625 Jamesferguson, which needs a better stage name.

Around 3 pm our meeting gradually dissolved, to be resumed another day.

Meade LX200 Work at TAO: Mon 26 Aug 2024

Before our Board Meeting broke up about 3 pm, David had suggested a trip to TAO that afternoon, to work on whatever activities needed attention, and to support Noah, who would be teaching his astronomy class at TAO that evening.

This suggestion was a bit of a surprise, and I had driven about 450 miles the day before, but I had been hoping to work in a trip to TAO to look at the Meade in the glow-dome, since it was hoped to add it to the instruments involved in recording occultations at TAO. Since much of the uncertainty was about how to use external software such as CPWI to communicate with the pier-mounted Celestron CGE mount, I in particular wanted to look carefully at the connections available on the mount. As it is somewhat vintage, it relied on connectors that are no longer in common use in amateur astronomy, such as what might be rj-11 [but proved to be rj-12] and rj-45 type sockets. In anticipation of trying to connect my CPU to the mount I had purchased several likely rj to USB adapter cables, and wanted to see if any of them showed promise.

After some confusion about who needed a ride and who didn't (Rob was committed elsewhere), I drove myself to TAO, and arrived at about 5:45 pm.

David was already at work trying to control the Meade's Celestron mount using Sky Safari on Noah's tablet (I believe), and things were working in some partial sense. Slews executed with this unit however sometimes seemed unconvincing.

Meade LX200 Work at TAO: Mon 26 Aug 2024

Once David took a break I tried my cables. My rj-45 to USB cable was irrelevant because those two Ethernet-style sockets were already occupied by cables and plugs from the RA and Dec motors, with socket labels “Dec Port” and “RA Port.” Above these was a stamp confirming that this was indeed a Celestron CGE mount. (See image below.) There were 5 more smaller, identical rj-style sockets on the mount, labelled PC, auto guide, aux1, aux2, and hand control. (See image next page.) The aux2 socket was occupied by a Celestron SKYsync GPS unit, which also offered a small rj-style socket that looked identical to the 5 on the mount. A Celestron NexStar* hand controller was plugged into the hand control socket. Finally there was a small coaxial power cord socket, with a power plug inserted.

6:13 pm Eastern, 26 Aug 2024 at TAO, showing the leftmost rj-45 “Dec” and “RA” ports with cables, the SKYsync GPS unit, and above the gold ring, on the left side, a stamp confirming on close inspection that this is indeed a Celestron CGE mount.

Meade LX200 Work at TAO: Mon 26 Aug 2024

“Take me to your leader.” 6:14 pm Eastern: Here one sees the 5 mount sockets that didn’t quite fit the rj-11 plugs on my rj11-USB connectors. Perhaps they are rj-12? [Note from 29 Aug: Yes, they are rj-12.]

Meade LX200 Work at TAO: 26 Aug 2024

Although my rj-45 and rj-11 to USB cables found no appropriate sockets on the mount and were therefore useless, I was amazed to discover that my rj-9 to USB cable DID fit the rj socket in the back of the hand controller. Thinking that this was probably too lucky and too easy to be the solution to mount-CPU connectivity, I nonetheless connected my CPU (a Dell Win 10 Pro) to the CGE through my rj-9 to USB cable plugged into the HC, turned on CPWI, and told it to connect by USB (implicitly to any USB-accessible Celestron mount). CPWI displayed “trying to connect” circles for a while, and then made a most unpleasant fail noise, and displayed a popup about what connections were possible. It may have mentioned preferring a NexStar+ hand controller. Perhaps there has been an upgrade since the NexStar* HC in the dome? One little slip... I later checked at home, and my old but probably more recent hand controller is indeed a NexStar+, and has a small modified tiny USB socket instead of an rj-9. Could that be the answer? I decided to pursue that route in future.

Since none of my rj to USB cables had worked in connecting my CPU to the CGE mount, as an alternative means of control I began playing with the Celestron NexStar* hand controller. After all I had used one for many years, until as recently as Dec 2021, when I switched to CPWI. Unfortunately the dome contained no manual for the hand controller (or even for the CGE mount itself), so this was a matter of button guesswork and slow hunt and peck, hoping to stimulate some dormant memories of hand controller technique. Gradually I recalled some functions, and remembered that the HC operations were a complicated set of nested trees of commands, which you navigated using Up / Down keys to work through a cyclical set of commands, and Undo to back up to the next level. The top level was a friendly “CGE Ready,” from which “List” let you select sets of objects such as named stars, double stars, variable stars, constellations, solar system, etc. Choosing constellations for example lets you cycle through all 88, and when you choose one you can select from a set of named stars. Under CGE Ready -> Menu -> Utilities I again found a set of useful commands, such as Go To Home, which sent the mount to a safe looking storage position. (See image next page.)

Meade Work at TAO: Mon 26 Aug 2024

Another very useful HC command I rediscovered, which people seemed unfamiliar with, was CGE Ready -> Menu -> Go To RA/Dec. This allowed one to enter desired object RA and Dec coordinates with reasonable accuracy, following which Enter would execute a slew to the specified coordinates. This would be essential for asteroid occultation work, as well as for simply going to a location without having to find a nearby named object in the HC database.

Selecting “Go To Home” with the hand controller led the Meade to move itself into this very plausible storage position. The hand controller may have earned a future in Meade related activities.

Meade Work at TAO: Mon 26 Aug 2024

As Noah had now completed his class (*ca.* 9 pm), he reappeared and I showed him the HC commands I had found. After slewing to several stars we decided to run through the HC's two-star alignment procedure. I think we used Kaus Borealis and Tarazed for basic alignment. I found it very difficult to contort myself into the right position to use both the crosshair finder scope and the no-crosshair OTA eyepiece being used. Kaus Borealis was comfortable; Tarazed, not so much. We then added three more calibration stars, including Antares, Caph, and another that I forget. Was it Arcturus?

After aligning we tried a slew to the location in Scutum of the coming 31 Aug 2024 occultation opportunity, RA 18 23 23.3 and Dec -09 56 24. The field was rather dark (this is f10 after all), I think Noah said he could make out three stars. No star-field comparisons were possible without a camera, and we didn't know how large the f.o.v. was, so we left it at that. My what a lot of background research needs to be carried out on this system. Noah recalled that "Hibernate" is the HC command for "stop, but recall the current alignment for next time," and we completed and shut down Meade operations with that command, at about 10 pm Eastern 26 Aug 2024.

A few additional observations:

The cable needed to connect my NexStar+ HC to my PC is a USB type A - Mini USB. I now have several on order. [And I found one at home on 29 Aug.]

In rj cables, "rj" stands for "registered jack." They are variants of the original single-telephone plug, called rj-11. This most often has 6 positions and 4 contacts (6P4C); it may instead be (6P2C). (A position P is a channel, which may be empty; a contact C means an actual wire. rj-9, which is physically smaller than rj-11, is (4P4C). rj-12 is larger, with (6P6C). rj-45 (8P8C) is similar to Ethernet, although different wiring patterns are used in rj-45 variants.

Meade Work at TAO: Mon 26 Aug 2024

Recommendations to date, and subsequent *actions*:

1) Mount a green laser pointer on the OTA. It already has a bracket.

[done by tb, 2 Sep]

2) Align the OTA and the finder, they are currently not in good common alignment.

[done by tb and rf, 2 Sep, or at least improved; applies to the laser pointer as well]

3) Add a 90 degree extension to the finder, or find a finder that has one.

4) Procure an illuminated reticle eyepiece for the OTA, so accurate centering can be done during alignment.

[with CPWI mount control, a camera may now suffice]

5) Note that the difficulties associated with aligning using the OTA inside the dome due to awkward orientation will disappear once it has a dedicated camera.

[see above]

Meade Work at TAO: Thu 29 Aug 2024, when nothing worked.

I had several reasons for wanting to work on the Meade on Thu 29 Aug 2024. The most important was CPWI. On 26 May I had been unable to connect CPWI to the CGE through the HC; a CPWI popup notification repeatedly stated:

Unable to communicate with any Celestron devices: Please verify that the USB or USB-to-serial cable is connected to the mount, accessory, or hand-controller. Please note: The only hand-controllers that are supported are the NexStar+ and StarSense hand-controllers.

The HC then being used in the glow-dome (on 26 Aug) was an older NexStar* with an rj-9 socket in the base; this HC was not on CPWI's approved list. On checking at home I found that my Celestron HC was a NexStar+, the approved model. Instead of an rj-9 connection in the base, it used a USB Type A to USB Mini cable, and after searching at home I found one of those. So I was ready to try connecting CPWI to CGE through my NexStar+ HC.

And even if that didn't work, the homebrew dongle to connect a CPU to the CGE by USB *or* WiFi promised by John Gall on Cloudy Nights had just arrived in the mail that very day, 29 Aug. So, I was confident that I would be able to connect CPWI to the CGE mount soon after my arrival at TAO on 29 Aug.

So, Rob and I arrived at TAO on the very hot afternoon of Thu 29 Aug (my van recorded an outside temp of 97F on the I-40) about 6:00 pm. I tried the CPU(CPWI) to CGE connection using my NexStar+ HC. That failed to connect. (Hmm, I had been confident that it would work.) Next I tried the dongle with jumper in place (wired usb option), connecting CPU(CPWI) to CGE directly (no HC). That failed. It was unclear whether to connect the rj-12 cord from the dongle to the HC or Aux socket on the CGE. It didn't matter, as both failed.

TAO: Thu 29 Aug 2024.

Meanwhile, in the TAO main building, Noah's meets with his class of bright young astronomy students. This is 6:08 pm Eastern, 29 Aug 2024, the passage of time being an illusion.

Meade Work at TAO: Thu 29 Aug 2024, when nothing worked.

Next I removed the jumper on the homebrew dongle and tried a direct CPU(CPWI) to CGE WiFi connection. That failed. Next we tried watching the faint indicator lights on the dongle. The sheet of written instructions from John Gall said that we should see a red led on the dongle, then a blue flash, then three short blue flashes. We saw red and sometimes blue, but never the final three blue ones. Occasionally Noah would stop by from his class and ask how things were going, and we told him that nothing worked.

This was all very discouraging, it was one of those nights in which one tries all options and just encounters a brick wall. In addition, when we tried the WiFi option we encountered a whole new fail message:

Unable to communicate with any Celestron devices: Please verify that the computer is connected to the wireless network of the WiFi module or, if using access-point mode, that specified network

Almost the only success we encountered was that our CPUs' WiFi and networking monitors did show that they were connecting to the dongle's own WiFi network, called *Homebrew-DDFD7C*.

Having succeeded at almost nothing, except that the NexStar+ HC continued to work when connected directly to the CGE, we gave up and left TAO about 9:30 pm.

In any case it was clear that the weather on 31 Aug 2024 would be bad, so the original motivation of using the CGE to record the occultation by 5625 Jamesferguson on that evening was no longer a possibility.

Meade Work at TAO: Thu 29 Aug 2024, when nothing worked.

David Fields and Rob Fowler in the Meade LX200 glow-dome on Thu 29 Aug 2024, the day when nothing worked.

Meade Work at LRO: Fri 30 Aug 2024, an HC success.

As a follow-on home (LRO) exercise the next day, I assembled my tripod and CGX mount, and tried to use the homebrew dongle with WiFi to connect my CPU(CPWI) to my CGX. No success, all the same fail messages. (Except that my standard CPWI – usb – CGX PC port connection still worked.) Again the closest thing to a success was seeing that the CPU connected to the dongle's WiFi network, Homebrew-DDFD7C. I varied several WiFi security settings with no effect, even turning off the Windows Defender Firewall.

Similarly the wired (usb) dongle option failed to connect the CPU(CWPI) to the CGX.

However I DID have one surprising success. When I tried using my NexStar+ HC as a bridge between the CPU(CPWI) and the CGX, specifically

CPU(CPWI) – USB Mini – NexStar+[HC] – rj-12 – CGX[Aux port],

that worked! (Something similar had seemingly **not** worked at TAO using the Nexstar+ HC, but at that time the HC's rj-12 plug may have been connected to the CGE's HC port rather than an Aux port.)

I proceeded to have a good time using CPWI to slew the CGX mount and tripod around its Northern hemisphere, varying the choice of the CPU's USB port from Aux1 to Aux2 and back, to make sure that this link was robust. It was.

The view window of the Nexstar+ HC displayed an exciting new message during this successful link, it said cryptically

Boot loader serial pass through 19.2K.

This setup continued to work on 31 Aug and 1 Sep, running CGX with CWPI felt like playing with a model train set. A picture follows.

Meade Work at LRO: Sun 1 Sep 2024, another disaster!

Here one can see the successful connection of CPWI on my CPU to my CGX mount, using my NexStar+ HC, 8:55 pm Eastern, 1 Sep 2024. It was fun using CPWI to steer the mount across the sky. Alas shortly afterwards, about 9:15 pm, my CPU had an unrecoverable hard drive crash. “Boy when things go wrong.”

ORION Board Meeting : Mon 2 Sep 2024

Having successfully connected CPWI to my CGX at my home observatory LRO, I was enthusiastic to try the same approach at TAO with the CGE mount. After my hard drive crash on 1 Sep I was less enthusiastic, but since Rob had the same CPWI software already installed on his CPU, I was still interested in trying this HC connection at TAO.

I encouraged my colleagues to consider a trip to TAO on Monday 2 Sep 2024 afternoon, after our regular astronomy lunch meeting at ElCantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge at 1:00 pm (Art, David and Rob were present). Amusingly, both David and I turned up at the restaurant with (rather scarce) Celestron WiFi dongles, in nearly identical packaging. I had just rediscovered mine, which I had last used about 6 years before.

After some discussion it appeared that there was interest in a Dark Stargaze evening on that date, so we broke up around 3 pm, planning to reconvene at TAO around 7 pm that evening.

The 2 Sep 2024 ORION Board Meeting in progress.
L to R: Rob, Slinky, Art, Ted and David. Image credit: Carina.

Dark Stargaze of Mon 2 Sep 2024:

Work on the Meade, when everything worked.

Rob Fowler and I arrived at TAO about 6:40 pm, about 20 minutes before planned, and found Art already at the TAO gate. David was reportedly possibly en route, but also possibly having second thoughts. After all, 29 Aug had been about 3.5 hrs of unsuccessful attempts to communicate with the Meade's Celestron CGE mount from CPWI, on a very hot day.

6:46 pm Eastern, Mon 2 Sep 2024 at TAO. A beautiful sky welcomes our new attempts to communicate with the CGE mount in the glow-dome. Art (at left) has come along with his Seestar S50, seizing the opportunity to do some new astrophotography on a nice night.

First we set up the HC connection as I had done at LRO, from CPWI on Rob's CPU through a USB type A to Mini cable connected to the base of my Nexstar+ HS, then through it's main rj-12 cable to the Aux1 port on the GCE. Nada. The same old CPWI popup appeared about no Celestron devices. We tried several variations, still no connection. HOW VERY DISCOURAGING.

About 7:20 pm with little enthusiasm I suggested we next try my Celestron WiFi dongle, which had not worked at home. We identified the Network name and joined it, and then tried to connect from CPWI as a WiFi connection. The screen painted a long vertical column of Celestron services and devices being searched for w/o success, "circles in the air" ... *and then it connected.*

Dark Stargaze of Mon 2 Sep 2024:

Work on the Meade, when everything worked.

Getting the WiFi connection working from Rob's CPU running CPWI to the Meade's Celestron GPE mount with the WiFi dongle in Aux1 was an unexpected success. Of course a WiFi connection was much preferred to using a hand controller, but there were many WiFi settings that might have blocked any connection. And yet it worked. After trying without success for over a week to connect CPWI to the CGE, we were finally in!

(above) Rob Fowler being amused by the successful WiFi connection from his CPU (table at left) to the Celestron CGE mount under the 12" Meade LX200.

Dark Stargaze of Mon 2 Sep 2024:

Work on the Meade, when everything worked.

Next, about 8:00 pm, I added a laser pointer with a pointing bracket to the Meade, which was straightforward because a suitable base attachment bracket was already present on the OTA. This is a very useful addition for seeing just where the OTA is pointing, and for locating objects in the sky; very useful for teaching. One minor problem, the laser pointer only has a pushbutton on the barrel; another fitting is needed to keep the laser on as long as desired.

I had also brought an illuminated reticle eyepiece for the OTA; this is essential for accurate visual alignment. Otherwise the only crosshair is in the finder, and the finder and OTA were not in good relative alignment. We did our best to align them using the illuminated reticle, and to align the new laser pointer as well. We added a CPWI pointing set of about 5 stars using the illuminated reticle, and saved the alignment. From then onwards each slew to a new object that evening ended with the object in the f.o.v. of the Meade OTA eyepiece.

I also had my ZWO ASI294MCP camera, but in my rush to pack I had left my main cable box at home, so I was without the USB3.0 camera cable needed for astrophotography. We accordingly decided that this would be a visual astronomy night. This was not necessarily a bad development; it was fun using CPWI to slew the Meade around with some precision. And this was a clear night; the views through the Meade were enjoyable. We visited the Lagoon Nebula (M8) and the impressive open cluster M7 (a very nice binocular object) in Sagittarius, Saturn in Aquarius (the nearly edge-on rings gave it a striking barred-circle appearance), the Andromeda galaxy (nucleus anyway; J2000.0 coords recorded were RA 00 42 00, Dec 41 09 35), M13 in Hercules (lovely, with faint granular stars easily visible), and finally, a stop by T CrB (a.k.a. HR5958) to confirm that it had not yet erupted.

All in all, a very pleasant night of observing, helped tremendously by using CPWI to slew to new objects. And using the laser pointer was fun too.

Dark Stargaze of Mon 2 Sep 2024:

Work on the Meade, when everything worked.

As a final “Success!” image, this is a CPWI screen shot taken when adding the final alignment star, Unukalhai. This is about 9:30 pm Eastern, Monday 2 Sep 2024.

Dark Stargaze of Thu 5 Sep 2024:

Sunset	8:00 pm
Civ dusk	8:26 pm
Ast dusk	9:29 pm
Moonset	9:14 pm
Moon illum.	3%

As the 12" Meade LX200 was now easily controllable by WiFi using CPWI, and a beautifully clear night was predicted for Thu 5 Sep, we decided to have a Dark Stargaze at TAO that evening, motivation and goals primarily being astrophotography.

As Rob was not feeling sufficiently motivated for this outing, I brought my own antique Win 7 laptop, since it had both CPWI and SharpCap installed. I arrived close to 7:00 pm. David arrived somewhat later with a newish Dell provided by Roane State, on which he had installed both programs as well.

The sky on 5 Sep was strikingly blue. Our initial attendees were Noah (who was teaching a class), myself (Ted Barnes) and Art Allison. The sky not long after sunset (8:14 pm Eastern) in the West looked something like this:

Dark Stargaze of Thu 5 Sep 2024:

Once Noah opened up the glow-dome I set up my Win 7 CPU “Lacerta,” with an extra monitor, near the dome, inserted my Celestron WiFi dongle in the Aux1 port of the CGE, switched the mount power on, and started CPWI. This was actually a slow setup because Lacerta was not familiar with the wired mouse and wired keyboard I had brought, or the 4-port USB extension. After the startup process found drivers and confirmed a connection to the dongle’s network Celestron-3E, 65 Mbps, 5 bars, I was able to start. I soon got the CPWI Notification popup “Unable to communicate with any Celestron devices.” Oh not again. Using Run as Admin I was able to get CPWI to connect to CGE, then set CPWI to the right TAO coordinates, and did a test move to Alrai. This seemed ok. But soon the CGE connection dropped. Usually it failed to reconnect. Rebooting was seldom helpful. My few successful attempts to connect CPWI to the CGE mount soon lost the link. Was Win 7 too antique for this application?

David suggested I try a newer laptop he had procured from Roane State. Although it looked promising on startup, and recognized and connected to the dongle wireless network Celestron-3E, CPWI was never able to connect to the CGE. After failing at this for some time, I noticed that in the Privacy and Security section one had to select which apps were allowed to pass through the firewall. The checkbox for CPWI had not been selected. Aha? Was this the answer? Perhaps. Unfortunately allowing CPWI external access required an admin name and pwd, which Dave didn’t have. So we had to defer testing this possible solution to the connectivity problem.

Next Dave came up with another laptop, his own PC, a Dell, and suggested we try that one. It was now about 11:00 pm and I was wearing thin, but we tried it with CPWI, and it connected! Several slews seemed ok (but were not carefully checked). I suggested Saturn, which found collective approval (it had been lovely 3 days earlier), and used CPWI to slew to Saturn. This was all wrong. We could see Saturn, but the OTA was pointing much lower. Had the alignment been lost?

Dark Stargaze of Thu 5 Sep 2024:

I rebooted CPWI, thinking that a new alignment was needed. Fortunately I noticed that the observatory coordinates, which CPWI displays on startup, were wrong. The longitude was something like 118 deg West; CPWI noted that its location was a few km from Los Angeles. Aha, David had downloaded CPWI, but hadn't yet set the coordinates to TAO.

I reset the coordinates and asked CPWI to slew to Saturn. The laser attached to the OTA confirmed that the new direction was now very close to Saturn. A success at last!

Through this evening Art had been working with his Seestar S50, and captured some lovely images. He was also playing music from a streaming service, something along the lines of "Music from the Hearts of Space" from earlier decades. At one stage, about 11:40 pm, the music shifted to a dreamy version of the Blue Danube Waltz. This seemed perfect for the dark night and its clouds of stars.

Soon after midnight we began shutting down, and departed about 12:30 am. No new Meade astrophotography yet, alas, which I had hoped for, but we now had a better understanding of the CGE connection problem, and could hope for new CPU-controlled Meade astrophotography on our next encounter.

ORION and TAO Last Month/ 7 Sep 2024: 1st Sat Public Stargaze

Sunset	7:58 pm
Civ dusk	8:23 pm
Ast dusk	9:25 pm
Moonset	10:03 pm
Moon illum.	17%

Saturday 7 Sep was the third in our 2024 series of 1st Sat Public Stargaze events. (We switched from a Jan-Jun 2024 3rd Sat series to better align with the New Moon's dark skies.)

This image, taken at 7:15 pm Eastern, soon after our arrival, shows what a remarkably beautiful sky we enjoyed during this event.

ORION and TAO Last Month/

7 Sep 2024: 1st Sat Public Stargaze

Astronomers David, Art, Rob and Sunny the Astrodog setting up and preparing for the Public Stargaze. Still 7:15 pm Eastern.

Visitors in the TAO main building listening to welcoming remarks, 8:22 pm. We eventually counted over 30 visitors for this Public Stargaze, probably due to the excellent weather and beautiful skies.

ORION and TAO Last Month/

7 Sep 2024: 1st Sat Public Stargaze

This event was also a debut for the 12" Meade LX200 for public viewing, with CPWI computer control for pointing and tracking. With CPWI running and the telescope well aligned it was straightforward to switch between celestial objects of public interest. On this evening Saturn (in Aquarius) was the main attraction, due to the remarkably narrow opening angle of the rings, so we simply used CPWI to slew to Saturn, which many people enjoyed seeing. (CPWI worked well on Rob's Acer laptop.) With a 19 mm Celestron Luminos eyepiece in the OTA we saw a larger image than in the 8" refractor, which gave people a nice comparison of Saturn images in two instruments.

This 395 px sq. cropped image was captured at 10:57 pm Eastern; after the public viewing session we attached a ZWO ASI294MCP camera to the OTA. To counteract atmospheric turbulence and avoid overexposure we used a fast single frame, 33 ms, at a low gain of 200. Post processing was used mainly to remove stuck-on colored pixels, since the camera cooler wasn't used in this preliminary attempt at LX200 astrophotography.

ORION and TAO Last Month/

7 Sep 2024: 1st Sat Public Stargaze

This elegant view of Neptune and Triton in Pisces is a single exposure of 4sG570, captured at 11:34 pm Eastern 7 Sep 2024 on the Meade LX200, with post processing to enhance color and especially to remove many stuck-on color pixels. Note the contrasting colors of pale blue Neptune (mag +7.8) and orange Triton (mag +13.5). The two brighter stars in this image are GSC 5253:976 above and 5253:965 below, both mag +12.3. With careful inspection one can identify fainter field stars down to mag +15.5.

n.b. At present these Meade LX200 images are left-right inverted.

ORION and TAO Last Month/

7 Sep 2024: 1st Sat Public Stargaze

This image of the rich Wild Duck open cluster (M11) in Scutum demonstrates the potential for producing lovely astrophotographs using the Meade LX200. This is a stack of 16 4-sec frames at a gain of 540, in our notation 16x4sG540. This is a full field image on the ASI294MCP (4144x2822 px), giving with this system an image of 22' x 15', about 0.3"/px. The small scale of these images resulted in obvious star trails for exposures of over *ca.* 30 secs, suggesting that more accurate alignment or a guiding system is needed. *n.b.* At present these Meade LX200 images are left-right inverted.

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Meadeian Developments:

Continued Work on the Meade LX200

21 Sep 2024

Sunset	7:37 pm
Civ dusk	8:02 pm
Ast dusk	9:03 pm
Moonrise	9:48 pm
Moon illum.	84%

The previous two months of the Trapezium included discussions of our attempts to upgrade the venerable 12" Meade LX200 (now housed in the glow-dome) for astrophotography. The initial problem was largely one of simple communication; both wired and wireless connections from an external CPU to the Celestron CGE pier mount within the dome that supports the Meade LX200 repeatedly failed, so our hope for external control and operation of the LX200 was not realized.

This changed on 2 Sep 2024, when we finally succeeded in connecting an external CPU running the Celestron - Plane Wave International program CPWI to the CGE mount, using a wifi connection from the CPU through a Celestron wifi dongle plugged into the CGE's Aux1 port.

Unfortunately there was a casualty during this period. My refurbished Dell Win 10 Pro laptop "Sapphire" that I have long used for all my telescope control lost contact with its hard drive on 1 Sep 2024 while I was experimenting with methods for controlling my Celestron CGX mount at my home observatory, LRO. There was no more communication with the hard drive, and nothing could be recovered. Fortunately my astrophotography and work for ORION were backed up and saved elsewhere, so nothing irreplaceable was lost. On 20 Sep Sapphire's defunct KingFast 512 GB Hard Drive was replaced by a 1TB Solid State Drive by Advanced Computers of Knoxville, who also restored its Win 10 Pro operating system. I am happy to recommend them to anyone who needs fast, competent work done on their CPU.

Testing my now refurbished laptop Sapphire was one of my principal goals for the 21 Sep trip to TAO with David Fields and Rob Fowler. In preparation for

this trip I downloaded essential astronomy software; SharpCap Pro, CPWI and PHD2 guiding, as well as Firefox and the current ASCOM platform. I arrived at TAO around 6:20 pm, and found less than perfect skies (see below).

**TAO skies to the North, 6:39 pm Eastern, 21 Sep 2024.
Sunny enjoyed his ham and cheese roll, and we ours.**

Although the skies were not outright bad, they were somewhat more than 50% overcast, and this fraction seemed to worsen through the evening, with considerable low-lying cloud and mist. This was ok for a debugging session, but observing was very limited, and astrophotography was not even attempted.

David's main interest during this trip was in considering the placement of new domes and walkways on the TAO site, so we first considered suggestions for these, and proposed a few largely aesthetic changes.

Next, in setting up the Meade I plugged my Celestron wifi dongle into the CGE's Aux1 socket, and on my second try at connecting I remembered to join the Celestron-3E wifi network, and started up CPWI as an administrator. For the first time I can recall I was then actually presented with the long promised "allow access" screen to allow use of this wifi network. About 8:00 pm, after a dramatic connect-time delay, I was very happy to see that CPWI had succeeded in establishing a link with the CGE mount. This was the first successful Meade connection for Sapphire, since it had lost its hard drive the night before our first attempt at making this CPWI-CGE wifi connection at TAO (2 Sep). The "first wireless Meade connection" honor went to Rob's PC.

As I started the alignment procedure in CPWI I noticed that this fresh install showed an incorrect location; just as with our earlier attempt to use CPWI with David's RSCC CPU, my software assumed it was still near Los Angeles. And since I had not brought my astronomy notes for this equipment debugging session, I didn't have TAO's actual coordinates handy. However I was surprised to notice that the copy of CPWI running on Sapphire had detected the GPS that had long ago been installed on the CGE, which was now powered on and plugged into the Aux2 port. As I watched, the coordinates CPWI displayed changed to W 84° 37' 03.5" and N 35° 49' 56.4", differing only slightly from the W ... 04.3" and N ... 56.7" I use when setting up at the West end of the concrete pad.

Rob and I proceeded to align the system using the rather few convenient stars that were bright enough to show clearly through the scattered clouds, using my 12mm Meade illuminated reticle as the aligning eyepiece. We recorded seven alignment stars, including (I think) Arcturus, Alkaid, Alpheratz, Scheat, Caph and Kochab. (These were saved as the CPWI star alignment pointing model file 09212024.pxp .)

Next we attempted to use the All Sky Polar Alignment feature of CPWI. This first reported the polar axis alignment errors, W 11' 59" and S 17' 52", and then requested that I select one of the stars near the Southern horizon indicated on the CPWI display screen. Arcturus proved to be at the tree line, so we instead slewed to Shaula, and following CPWI's instructions, centered it in the eyepiece and selected "Centered." The mount then slews to where the star would be if the mount were perfectly polar aligned. One next uses the mount's Alt and Azi controls to again center that star in the eyepiece; the mount is then polar aligned.

Alas neither Rob nor I know where these manual Alt and Azi adjustment controls were located on the CGE mount, so we could not complete the ASPA polar alignment exercise. We just left the routine at that point. Before our next visit to TAO we will have read the CGE manual and learned about these controls, so we will be able to complete CPWI's ASPA polar alignment of the CGE.

Although we could not complete the polar alignment, our existing alignment was good enough to take us close to a few objects for some quick observing. We first slewed to Saturn and admired the image using the two very different eyepieces I had brought, a 7 mm Nagler and a 40 mm Plössel. In the Nagler we had a clear, highly magnified image of Saturn, and I had the impression I could occasionally see the narrow ring in front of the planet. In the Plössel the image of Saturn was of course much smaller, but occasionally with some blinking the image became very sharp.

As a last exercise we tried adding a photoreducer and then a Meade telenegative Barlow to the system, but there were too few faint stars visible in this cloudy, misty sky to allow the effect of these changes to be evident. One needs a list of bright doubles to use as test objects to show how the field has changed.

Finally, about 10:30 pm we enjoyed watching a pearly moon rise through a very thick cloudy haze. No features could be distinguished.

So, although we accomplished no astrophotography, CPWI on my newly restored laptop Sapphire had worked essentially flawlessly with the Meade's CGE mount. So, the evening was a very pleasant experience, despite the limited seeing.

Shutdown and departure were around 11 pm on 21 Sep.

Preparing for an evening interaction of CPU and CPWI with the pier-mounted CGE mount and its 12" Meade LX200, about 6:40 pm Eastern, 21 Sep 2024.

New recommendations for the Meade LX200, and subsequent actions:

- 1) The laser pointer needs a ring barrel bracket with a set screw, to allow the laser to be left on when needed. (David and Don expressed some concern about potentially overabundant laser light.)

On 5 Oct I brought a micrometer to TAO to measure the laser tube diameter. However I got distracted. Assuming the laser is the same size as the one on my Mak-Newt at LRO, the o.d. is about 21.6 mm.

- 2) Polar Aligning the Meade using All Sky Polar Alignment (ASPA) on CPWI, as we attempted on 21 Sep, requires knowledge of the operation of the CGE mount's Alt and Azi pointing adjustments. Ted and Rob need to read the CGE manual to learn how to make these adjustments. Following this they should realign the CGE on a clear night with ample stars. They should complete this exercise by aligning the finder and laser pointer with the OTA itself.

On 5 Oct Rob found that the OTA and laser pointer were already well aligned. The finder however was not. We still haven't read (or found) the CGE manual, so ASPA is yet to be carried out on the Meade.

- 3) The next development will be to implement guiding, presumably using the PHD2 guiding program. A suitable guide camera should be procured. It will be easiest to use this with the existing finderscope, if feasible.

Don Spong offered us a lovely guide scope assembly he was not currently using, but on 5 Oct 2024 we found that its mounting bracket didn't correspond to what was available on the Meade OTA.

- 4) The storage location for pointing model files (saved star alignment datasets) in CPWI should be identified. It may be possible to share these between CPUs.

On 3 Oct 2024: I found the pxp file cited 3 pages previously as an example at C:\Users\(\Username)\Documents\09212024.pxp .

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ORION EIC Board Meeting

30 Sep 2024

Our regular repeating weekly Monday 1:00 pm lunch ORION Board Meeting and astronomy discussion took place as usual at the ElCantarito Mexican Restaurant in Oak Ridge. Attending were (L to R) Eclipsemeister Juan Carbajo, Trapezium Editor Ted Barnes (moi), Secretary and IT Person Rob Fowler, Former Flyboy Art Allison and TAO Director David Fields. Soon after ordering lunch and discussing many, many things, such as the sentence “What hath Wrob Writ?,” we proceeded to the astronomical business at hand.

ORION Board Meeting, 30 Sep 2024; Juan Carbajo, Ted Barnes, Rob Fowler, Art Allison and David Fields.

The topic of greatest interest appeared to be one that was initiated at last week's 23 Sep Board Meeting, which was to explore the options for establishing a remotely accessible telescope facility at TAO. This would likely start as part of the ongoing upgrades of the Meade LX200, and then perhaps proceed to other telescopes currently housed at TAO.

In an email dated 28 Sep 2024, Don Spong expressed considerable enthusiasm for such a facility. He noted in particular that

"A remote telescope would give us the capability to do long exposures and exposures at awkward times in the middle of the night. This could be very helpful for occultations, faint objects, and recording exoplanet crossings. Also, there have been clear evenings when I or others wanted to go out to Tao, but couldn't find anyone with a key to go out and let us in. ... I think a remote scope would provide us with new capability to extend our science mission that we don't currently have."

This was in part a response to David's concern that a remote telescope facility might reduce our visits to TAO.

Personally I am in agreement with Don about the "science" advantages of having access to a remote telescope at inconvenient hours, when people might not be interested in visiting TAO in any case. I would not be surprised if my rate of occultation reporting was doubled or tripled by having access to such a facility.

Visiting TAO and participating in Public Stargaze events is in any case an enjoyable part of the local astronomy experience for many of us; and since a remote facility would likely need considerable tinkering, I suspect that my "TAO time" would only be increased by this new attraction. And seeing that our group has the enthusiasm and abilities needed to set up a remote telescope facility may encourage more public participation in our activities; "They are doing really neat stuff."

Images taken on the Meade LX200 last month showed that star trailing was a potential problem, since this f10 telescope will likely require longer exposures to bring out faint objects. We are accordingly discussing installing guiding, likely using the popular and largely standard guiding program PHD2. The immediate questions are whether the current finderscope can be used as a guide scope, and what can be used as a guide camera. Alternatively, it may be possible to use a photoreducer to lower the system's focal length.

Your typical modern guidescope and camera assembly, which the Meade needs.

Since there remains considerable trial and error dabbling to be attempted with this system, there was a discussion regarding when we might next visit TAO to try some of these modifications. The next Public Stargaze is Sat 5 Oct, and a clear sky is predicted. However it might also be useful to have a clear night for Meade LX200 imaging tests on the night before we host visitors.

In support of a proposed remote telescope project (see two pages previous), Don sent David and I (Ted) pdfs of an article titled “Going Remote” by Ron Brecher, of Guelph in Ontario, about setting up a remote telescope; this was in the Sept 2024 issue of Sky and Telescope, pp.60-65. Given my interests I read the article enthusiastically, and was surprised to learn how straightforward this exercise might be. In particular, remote access to a telescope-controlling laptop could be arranged through a German program called AnyDesk, which is available in a free version for beginning users. I set up AnyDesk on several of my Windows machines at home, and was soon able to implement “remote” communication (within my home network) that allowed me to run the essential (for me) programs CPWI and SharpCap, and to capture images, control focusers and direct my CGX mount from a base PC some distance away. If this worked from a location external to my home network, I would consider the remote access telescope problem already largely solved! (Of course we will still need to protect the instruments from the weather.)

Image of an active AnyDesk display showing screens from both CPWI (at right) and SharpCap (at left) on my remote computer at LRO. 8:30 pm Eastern, 30 Sep 2024.

I tested the performance of this remote telescope system using AnyDesk on the afternoon of 1 Oct by setting up my Win 7 PC in the Clinton Public Library, and trying to connect to my refurbished Win 10 Pro Dell laptop at home in LRO (Lost Ridge Observatory), distance about 5.5 km. The target Win 10 Pro at LRO also had AnyDesk installed, but that program was left not running, as a test. The connection went through without difficulty, and I was able to start up CPWI and SharpCap on the remote Dell at LRO. I did a few tests including a slew from Polaris to Alderamin, and changed the ZWO EAF focuser setting (through a SharpCap data window) from 10000 to 12000. On my return to LRO just after 4 pm I found that my CGX mount was happily pointing towards Alderamin, and the focuser on the OTA had indeed moved out to 12000. (The OTA was not mounted on the CGX for these tests.) A subsequent check in LRO about 10 pm found the CGX still following Alderamin (then just crossing the median), and SharpCap was still open, awaiting image capture instructions. Presumably the next step would be to attempt remote astrophotography operation of the Meade LX200 at TAO, from a location external to TAO.

Our next opportunity to attempt remote telescope operation was on 5 Oct 2024, before the Public Stargaze. As often happens there were snags. The CPU at TAO used to connect to the Meade by Wifi dongle would also need to maintain a Wifi connection to one of TAO's internet links, so it could interact with the remote user. We had planned to use Rob's notebook for this, but it could only support a single Wifi connection, so we used my Dell Win 10 Pro laptop instead. For some reason my Dell had trouble maintaining simultaneous Wifi connections to the Meade and to the TAO internet. (I had forgotten my Celestron dongle for the Meade so we used David's, which may be an earlier model.) Then the crowd of happy visitors arrived so we were occupied until about 10:30 pm. We then connected my laptop ONLY to the Meade, which was more stable, and aligned on 5 stars. When that was finished, around 11:00 pm, Rob connected my ZWO ASI294MCP camera to the Meade and we captured a few test images. One was Vega; a single exposure of Vega and field stars in the Meade follows.

A single 8-sec exposure of Vega and field stars using the Meade LX200 with a ZWO ASI294MCP camera at a gain of 450, taken at 11:17 pm Eastern on 5 Oct 2024. This image was post-processed primarily for contrast, and was rotated by 180 deg to put North approximately at top. The expected f.o.v. is about 22'x15'. The brightest field star, up and slightly left of Vega, is 9.7 mag Tycho 3105:692. One is able to distinguish a surprisingly large number of much fainter field stars close to this bright first-magnitude star. My references list only a few of these field stars, which were evidently hidden in Vega's glare.

Success!

As a final exercise for the evening of 5 Oct 2024, Rob and I attempted to complete our “remote telescope” demo exercise at TAO by setting up his notebook inside the TAO main building, using AnyDesk to link to my Dell (adjacent to the glow-dome) through the internet. We then sent a remote image capture command to the active SharpCap program running on my Dell. This was successful; at 11:52 pm Eastern the Dell captured the image shown here. This is our first “remote telescope” image captured at TAO. Of course we plan to follow this demo with station separations greater than 17m!

This is the double-double star epsilon Lyrae (ϵ Lyr), showing both ϵ_1 Lyr (above) and ϵ_2 Lyr (below). This is a short exposure of only 8 ms, allowing the components of both double stars to be distinguished.

To the right is an extreme enlargement of the top double, ϵ_1 Lyr, clearly showing the double’s two components, which are separated by only about 2.6”. In the enlargement the separation appears to be about 8 px, as expected since each pixel in this image has a side of just 0.3”. (The image processing program unfortunately softened the pixels’ edges.) Clearly there is a coma-like distortion in the two star images which needs correction.

The successful demonstration of a working “remote telescope” system at TAO using the Meade LX200 (previous page) could not go uncelebrated. Here we see Rob Fowler at 11:50 pm Eastern running AnyDesk on his notebook, which shows a highly magnified image of ϵ_1 Lyr from the remote screen (blue image at right, in the dark SharpCap field). Rob attributed the success to “reconfiguring the emitter array to transmit an inverse tachyon pulse.” Art Allison and David Fields participated as signatories (note quill on desk). The successful capture of this remote image of ϵ_1 Lyr was followed by an improvisational performance of a vaguely musical nature.

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Saturn imaged at TAO, 11:02 pm Eastern 10 Oct 2024, using the Meade LX200.
This is a stack of 2000 frames captured by Rob Fowler, processed using Autostakkert and Registax.
Estimated ring opening angle 4.6° . Color intensity and sharpness enhanced in post-processing.

ORION and TAO Last Month/ ORION Meeting 16 Oct 2024

Speakers: David Fields and Ted Barnes

Title: TAO, Past, Present and Future: Group Discussion

In their presentations David Fields and Ted Barnes discussed past, present and future opportunities for the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO). This facility, managed by RSCC, is a unique East Tennessee resource that is valued by us all. The local astronomical community makes considerable use of this facility, and it has a long history as a successful site for public outreach programs in science, engineering and especially in astronomy.

Director David Fields introducing the topic of TAO.

David discussed some of the history of TAO, notably the work on radio astronomy and the construction of a series of radio dishes, which performed successfully but suffered from inclement weather. David suggested possibilities for reviving the work at TAO on radio astronomy, and discussed possibilities for development of the TAO campus, perhaps including more

observing sites and an extension of the active observing areas. A recent development is the work on upgrading the 12" Meade LX200 as a student and group instrument for astrophotography, e-observing, and as a remote telescope facility (RTF). Finally he mentioned possible future research activities at TAO, including asteroid occultation observations (ongoing), variable star observations, and exoplanet searches.

ORION and TAO Last Month/ ORION Meeting 16 Oct 2024

Speakers: David Fields and Ted Barnes

Title: TAO, Past, Present and Future: Group Discussion

Ted then reviewed recent work (Aug-Oct 2024) involving Rob Fowler on adapting the Meade LX200 as described above, and reviewed progress on using the Meade for astrophotography and as a remote telescope facility. He noted that a writeup of this ongoing work can and will continue to be found in the Trapezium. Some examples of Meade astrophotography were shown, including our first RTF images, captured at TAO on 5 Oct 2024. The next steps are to capture images at greater distances as a demo exercise, upgrade the TAO internet if necessary, and plan and construct a suitable weatherproof, remotely accessible, and secure dome.

Comments from the audience during this presentation included observations regarding difficulties with this Meade, notably a problematic fine focus; a concern regarding the reliability of CPWI; and the very important issue of the security of an RTF, in view of recent unauthorized entries into the TAO site.

First RTF demo image at TAO, 5 Oct 2024. (Meade to TAO building, distance 17m.)
This is the double-double ϵ Lyr, showing successful splitting of the 2.6" upper double.

21 Sep 2024 recommendations for the Meade LX200, and subsequent [actions](#):

- 1) The laser pointer needs a ring barrel bracket with a set screw, to allow the laser to be left on when needed. (David and Don expressed some concern about potentially overabundant laser light.)

A suitable laserpointerbuttonholderdownerthingie was assembled from electrical hardware bits and installed on the Meade's laser pointer by Ted and David on 19 Oct 2024. Later that evening as a remote exercise Ted and Rob carefully aligned the laser pointer with the OTA, using Vega and the laser pointer holder adjustment screws.

- 2) Polar Aligning the Meade using All Sky Polar Alignment (ASPA) on CPWI, as we attempted on 21 Sep, requires knowledge of the operation of the CGE mount's Alt and Azi pointing adjustments. Ted and Rob need to read the CGE manual to learn how to make these adjustments. Following this they should realign the CGE on a clear night with ample stars. They should complete this exercise by aligning the finder and laser pointer with the OTA itself.

Ted downloaded the current CGE Manual for this mount model from the Celestron website, and forwarded copies (pdfs) to Rob and David. Ted later reviewed the manual and identified the location of the Alt and Azi Allen-key adjustment screws and lock knobs. On 18 and 19 Oct Ted adjusted the Meade's polar alignment to better center on Polaris.

- 3) The next development will be to implement guiding, presumably using the PHD2 guiding program. A suitable guide camera should be procured. It will be easiest to use this with the existing finderscope, if feasible.

Don Spong offered us a lovely guide scope assembly that he was not currently using, but on 5 Oct 2024 we found that its mounting bracket didn't correspond to what was available on the Meade OTA. John Cliff proposed using an off-axis guider.

- 4) The storage location for pointing model files (saved star alignment datasets) in CPWI should be identified. It may be possible to share these between CPUs.

3 Oct 2024: Ted found the CPWI pxp files on his CPU "Sapphire" at C:\Users\(\Username)\Documents.pxp .*

ORION and TAO Last Month/ Remote Telescope Facility (RTF)

First Test at Distance

19 Oct 2024

Sunset	6:58 pm
Civ dusk	7:24 pm
Ast dusk	8:23pm
Moonrise	8:22 pm
Cometset	10:12 pm
Moon illum.	94%

Sat 19 Oct 2024

The advantages of having access to a remote telescope facility (RTF) at TAO that can be controlled from a more convenient location are obvious. One can capture images from a home site in Oak Ridge or Clinton without a 80 mile round trip for each session, one does not have to arrange access to a secure site for each imaging session, and one need not be physically present at the site for every event that one might like to record, such as an asteroid occultation at 4 am, when it is unlikely that one's colleagues can be persuaded to attend. Remote telescope setup sites can now be rented in the US at dark sky locations, such as in the Southwest, where the equipment is maintained by the facility owners. The problem is largely one of expense; these typically cost amounts starting about \$500 per month.

At TAO our needs are somewhat different; we already have access to a relatively dark site, and initially simply need remote access to a single telescope for development purposes. Our capabilities can advance with our experience and our growing needs.

Since Aug. 2024, with the encouragement of David Fields, Rob Fowler and I have been working to develop the Meade LX200 sited in the glow dome at TAO for this purpose. Initially we simply learned to do astrophotography with this instrument, using a directly attached ZWO ASI294MC-P camera. Next we took on the more difficult problem of communicating with the Celestron CGE mount that controls the Meade. Many approaches are suggested in the literature, but most failed when we attempted them. After some effort we succeeded in connecting to the CGE using a wireless Celestron dongle with an rj-12 plug, that we accessed from an external PC running the mount control program CPWI.

ORION and TAO Last Month/ Remote Telescope Facility (RTF)

First Test at Distance

19 Oct 2024

Since our PCs can operate two independent Wifi connections, it was possible to use a first PC cited adjacent to the Meade to communicate both with the Meade's CGE mount and with TAO's internet. A second PC could then talk to the first PC by Wifi, thereby controlling the Meade indirectly. In practice we implemented this by installing the German program AnyDesk on our PCs, which gives each PC an ID number so it can be connected to through the AnyDesk software. The second PC then sees the screen of the first PC (which is controlling the Meade), and the owner of that second PC can give commands to the software running on the first PC, thus using the first PC's software for example to move the OTA (using CPWI) or capture images (using SharpCap).

We had previously tested this system at TAO on 5 Oct, with a separation between the first PC (near the Meade) and the second PC (inside the TAO main building) of just 17m. Although this worked well, and we did a remote demo capture of ϵ Lyr, one would of course like to demonstrate use of this remote telescope system "at distance," meaning to demonstrate that it works well over the distances we are likely to encounter in practice, say between TAO and Oak Ridge (40 km) or TAO and Knoxville (60 km).

A nice opportunity for a test at distance arose on the Public Stargaze night of Sat 19 Oct 2024. Since Rob was not planning to attend this event and decided to stay in Oak Ridge, I aligned the Meade and set it up for wireless communication using my Win 10 Pro PC, with AnyDesk installed. I called Rob by cell phone so we would have an open line for communication, and he then used AnyDesk to contact my PC to request a remote session. I simply approved this request, and Rob was then able to use his mouse in Oak Ridge to give commands to CPWI and SharpCap on my screen. This required considerable "tuning" of the AnyDesk application, such as the Oak Ridge remote user learning how to view the Meade PC control screens "full size."

ORION and TAO Last Month/ Remote Telescope Facility (RTF)

First Test at Distance

19 Oct 2024

These learning exercises were largely a matter of trial and error experience, and the AnyDesk connection proved to be stable for long periods of time. Some aspects of the remote telescope experience were unusual and exciting, such as watching the OTA's laser pointer slew across the sky in response to commands from a user in Oak Ridge, 38.5 km distant. This with no one in the glow dome.

We also learned how to use the text "Chat" feature of AnyDesk and confirmed that one could send audio in duplex mode.

After Rob captured several images using SharpCap, we also learned how the remote user can use AnyDesk to transfer images he has saved on the Meade PC to his (the remote user's) PC; this is a simple copy and paste operation between the two screens. Even folders can be transferred in this manner. Thus it appears likely that one does not actually need a local PC user at TAO to operate this RTF; one can simply leave the TAO-based PC powered on, waiting for an external connection from any preapproved AnyDesk user.

The images we captured in this first TAO RTF at distance exercise were actually rather mundane. The first such, a 4 sec full field (4144x2822 px) single RGB24 exposure at a gain of 520, taken with the ASI294MC-P camera at 9:27 pm Eastern, is reproduced two pages following. This camera sensor was at room temperature (19.7 C) since this was a simple first attempt, so in post processing many colored "stuck on" pixels were removed. This image was also rotated by π to give the conventional (N up, E left) orientation, since the camera had inadvertently been attached in a rotated orientation. Applying the ASPS plate solver to this field gives coordinates of RA 17 34 06, Dec 12 34 25, f.o.v. 21'x14', $f_L = 3069$ mm (3048 mm expected), scale 0.311 arcsecs/px, $\theta_{\text{Cam}} = 4.25^\circ$. Focus required a camera body displacement of 3.0 cm, which may explain the long fitted focal length.

ORION and TAO Last Month/ Remote Telescope Facility (RTF) First Test at Distance

19 Oct 2024

Our first successful live long-distance remote telescope control experiment at TAO, *ca.* 10 pm Eastern, 19 Oct 2024. Pradeep, Art and Don watch while Ted (seated) monitors internet connectivity and local Wifi PC control of the TAO Meade LX200, and remote user Rob Fowler in Oak Ridge (38.5 km) employs AnyDesk with 1) SharpCap, to capture Meade images, and 2) CPWI, to move the OTA from star to star in long dramatic swooping laser-pointer-illuminated slews. This test was smoothed by an open cell phone connection. We also confirmed that AnyDesk can transfer two-way audio and text chat in this configuration. Image by David Fields.

**ORION and TAO Last Month/
Remote Telescope Facility (RTF)
First Test at Distance**

19 Oct 2024

Our first star field captured at TAO in response to a remote instruction (from Oak Ridge) in our first “Test at Distance,” using the Meade LX200 as a remote telescope facility. This field is in Ophiuchus, slightly NW of the bright star Rasalhague (α Oph), which is offscreen just to the left. The brightest star visible here is HD159391, a high proper motion K0 type star with a visual magnitude of 7.84. The faintest stars easily identifiable here are about magnitude 15.0. More details regarding this 1x4sG520 field are given in the text two pages previous.

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Dark Stargaze & Continued Work on the Meade LX200

Tue 26 Nov 2024

On Tuesday 26 Nov 2024, the day after our ORION Board Meeting of 25 Nov, I kept noticing the beautiful blue sky, and after checking the CSC chart for TAO and seeing that it was favorable, I started getting that old TAO feeling. I really felt like the Meade LX200 needed another attempt at a polar alignment; when last at TAO we had skipped that final part of the alignment exercise.

Sunset	5:27 pm
Civ dusk	5:54 pm
Ast dusk	6:57 pm
Moonrise	3:04 am
Moonset	2:50 pm
Moon illum.	26%

Tue 26 Nov 2024

I contacted David and Rob, who were both available for an improvisational Dark Stargaze, so we decided to meet at TAO around 6:30 pm. Due to holiday traffic I arrived about 6:40 pm, and Rob and David were already inside the gate. It was very dark. Jim Lord soon appeared as well. I set up my computer, ZWO ASI294MCP camera, and lots of cables and related components near the Meade glowdome, and prepared to align. Although Rob had some reservations, at my suggestion we abandoned the HC and proceeded using only my computer (connected to the Meade by Wifi dongle), running CPWI for OTA pointing, and SharpCap for precise imaging. This would be a camera-only align (no eyepieces used), except that we would also use the laser pointer on the Meade and my binoculars for coarse adjustments.

During initial alignment I first slewed to Kochab, and since the camera was WAY out of focus we had a large Airy disk. Associated with this was a surprise; there was an obvious irregularity in the image. (See next page.) After discussions spanning several days it seemed most likely that this was a problem within the Meade, perhaps an obstruction, or at worst, damage to a component such as the secondary mirror. Of course it might be due to a problem as simple as a misaligned camera. This disturbing discovery will be a topic for future investigation. For now, it does explain some problems with the Meade images, such as a tendency for bright stars to have asymmetric rays; these are the bright edge of the defect, as seen when close to the focal plane.

An Airy disk of Kochab captured by the Meade LX200 with a ZWO ASI294MCP camera (1-sec exposure, gain 520). Note the unexpected defect, the dark region with a bright edge at lower right.

Initially I kept losing the wired USB3.0 connection between my PC and the camera, which used a ZWO USB3.0 6' cable and a red colored JSAUX USB3.0 6' extension. Replacing the red JSAUX cable with a black ITD Itanda one solved the problem. (The “good” cable pair was left connected in storage at the end of the session.) We next added an additional seven alignment stars, these being Deneb, Altair, Enif, Fomalhaut, Diphda (β Ceti), Rigel, and Betelgeuse. The aeternal problem of a slight slow drift of a star to the left in the final stages of alignment is still present. Interestingly, a star on the other side of the Meridian (latter two) drifts in the opposite direction.

Next I selected “Perform ASPA,” and was told that the polar axis errors were West 9'40” and North 12'2”. (Not so terrible.) ASPA then told me to choose a

marked star. (Diphda was on offer, so I chose it.) Selecting it led to another Meridian flip (if I recall correctly), and ASPA next told me to use the Alt and Azi mount adjustment controls to recenter Diphda. The problem here was that the online 75 pp. CGE manual does not show where both mount adjustments are; the relevant Fig.2-10 and text on p.12 of the manual is shown below.

To adjust the mount in altitude:

1. Locate the altitude adjustment bolt just above the tripod column (see figure 2-10).
2. Using the 7/32" Allen wrench provided, turn the altitude adjustment bolt until the mount is at the right elevation.

The total altitude range is from 13° to 65°. With the 23 lb counterweight attached to the counterweight shaft, the equatorial head can go as low as 20° without hitting the tripod leg.

To adjust the mount in azimuth:

Fig.2-10 (not labeled in manual)

1. Locate the azimuth adjustment bolt on the flat portion of the tripod column (see figure 2-10).
2. Loosen the two azimuth lock knobs located on the top of the tripod column.
3. Turn the azimuth adjustment bolt with the 7/32" Allen wrench until the polar axis is pointing in the right direction.
4. Tighten the azimuth lock knobs to hold the mount in place. The mount can be moved $\pm 7^\circ$ in azimuth using these bolts.

Above: Section of the CGE manual indicating the Alt Adjustment bolt, but NOT the Azi Adjustment bolt. n.b. the Allen key required is 3/16", not the 7/32" stated in the manual.

Although the Alt adjustment bolt is clear in Fig.2-10, and could be turned with a 3/16" Allen key (NOT 7/32" as stated), according to Rob the resulting change in laser beam position near Diphda was unclear. As for the Azi adjustment bolt, it is nowhere identified in Fig.2-10, so it was not clear how to adjust the mount's Azi. I was able to move the mount "by hand" in large Azi steps after releasing the Azi lock knobs in Fig.2-10, so we used that and the Alt bolt to move the mount position in both axes. Using binoculars to improve

Dark Stargaze & Continued Work on the Meade LX200

Tue 26 Nov 2024

the agreement between the laser beam's position with the position of Diphda certainly improved our Polar Alignment, although the result appeared far from ideal. When we stopped this binocular-based procedure we noticed that Diphda was now visible on the SharpCap screen, together with the target circle, if not especially near it. Before adjusting Alt and Azi, Diphda had not been evident anywhere on the SharpCap screen.

For future reference, this is an image of the part of the CGE mount shown in Fig.2-10 on the previous page. The Alt adjustment bolt and one of the two propeller-like Azi locks are evident; both are indicated in Fig.2-10. However there is no indication in the manual's Fig.2-10 regarding which feature is the Azi adjustment bolt. Without this information, it's not clear how to perform a precise adjustment of the mount's Alt and Azi, as required for accurate Polar Alignment. Perhaps a query to Cloudy Nights is appropriate.

Dark Stargaze & Continued Work on the Meade LX200

Tue 26 Nov 2024

By this point it was growing late, and colder, and Rob was enthusiastic about actually capturing some images, so we decided to leave the alignment in the “better” condition we had reached. It was too late to find Saturn in a good position, so we proceeded to M42, and captured several images of the Orion Nebula using various filetypes. First, here is the classic “Oops, the laser pointer is still on” image. This was taken at 11:13 pm on Tue 26 Nov 2024, and is a single 1sG520 exposure, unprocessed.

This classic image includes an only very slightly misdirected OTA-fixed laser beam, pointing the way to M42, with the four stars of the Trapezium easily visible.

This is one (of many) of the later M42 images we captured, a stack of 115 png frames at a gain of 450, converted to a jpg. The 115 SharpCap stacking log timestamps are from 11:27:04 – 11:31:13 pm Eastern, 26 Nov 2024. This was inadvertently a mix of 77x1s and 38x4s frames. After conversion to a jpg some post-processing was applied, notably to increase contrast and bring out the red tint of H α light. Some downward-pointing scattered light is evident below the brightest stars, which is an artifact of the “blip” visible in the Airy disk in the image shown 4 pages earlier. Several “stuck-on” pixels were also removed in post-processing; since this was mainly a technical session we hadn’t bothered to attach the camera cooler.

Continued Work on the Meade LX200

Applying the ASPS (All Sky Plate Solver) to the unenhanced version of this full-field (4144x2822 px) image of M42 finds central coordinates of RA 05 35 01, Dec -05 22 15, a 21'x14' f.o.v. (21.64' x 14.74' expected), a fitted focal length of 3074 mm (3048 mm expected), a px scale of 0.311", and an image angle of 15.7 deg clockwise from N. (We had made no attempt to orient the camera.) The position is only about 4' from the nominal center of M42, near the Trapezium. If this is the location a slew arrived at after our alignment, it is rather good. Unfortunately I don't recall whether the slew to M42 was subsequently corrected by small iterative moves.

The mean star FWHM over the 115 frames was 5.8 px or 1.8" for 1s frames and 6.6 px or 2.1" for 4s frames. During the *ca.* 250 sec of these 115 exposures the frame drift in (x,y) in this unguided stack was about (-28", -13").

Next we used CPWI to slew to the "Christmas Tree" open cluster NGC 2264 in Monoceros. (Yes I was actually trying to reach the Christmas tree in Orion.) In any case I thought an open cluster would be good for magnitude tests. I captured single frames of 4sG450, 8sG450, 15sG520 and 30sG520. The faint star images were typically smeared over regions of about 5px x 10px. Each doubling of exposure time gave me about another magnitude in depth, and at 30sG520 I could just pick out the brighter 18th mag stars. (Aladin v.12 Gaia data was used as a reference.) Of course these large star image sizes are a problem, and need improvement in future. This may be the Airy disk problem.

Surprisingly, little trailing of star images was evident in these unguided exposures, even at 30s. Evidently our attempt at better polar alignment was successful. A post processed version of the single frame 30sG520 image is shown on the following page. The bright 4.7 mag star S Mon that dominates this cluster is a mess, again as expected due to the Airy disk problem, but the other faint stars have come out visibly close to pointlike.

The Christmas Tree open cluster in Monoceros, NGC 2264, captured at 11:36 pm Eastern, 26 Nov 2024, at TAO. The bright blue star near the cluster's center is S Mon, a mag 4.7 type O7V irregular variable in a multiple star system. Note the lack of star trailing in this 30s single unguided exposure. This image used a ZWO ASI294MCP on the Meade LX200, with some post-processing, primarily to remove the brighter stuck-on pixels. Stars are visible in this image down to about 18th mag.

Finally we captured a few test images of the Horsehead Nebula and of Mars, but as the sky had become increasingly overcast from around 11 pm Eastern, these images were not satisfactory, and are not shown here. We shut down and departed TAO around 12:30 am Eastern on 27 Nov 2024.

Dec 2024 Trapezium
pp. 46-53

Public / Dark Stargaze & Continued Work on the Meade LX200

Sat 07 Dec 2024

Our final scheduled Public Stargaze for the year 2024 was to be held on Sat 07 Dec. There was however a weather complication. Although the TAO skies for 5-7 Dec 2024 were predicted to be very clear and transparent, the nights of 5-6 and 6-7 Dec 2024 had been very cold, with minima of around 20F. Accordingly the maintenance people had shut off the water at TAO to prevent frozen pipes. Since there would be no toilet facilities available in the main building, David fields decided to cancel the Public Stargaze for Sat 07 Dec. However several ORION astronomers (Ted, Rob, Art and David) thought the very dark sky predicted should not be wasted, so after some online discussion we decided to hold an impromptu Dark Stargaze on that same night, starting at about 6 pm Eastern. (The Public Stargaze had been listed as starting at 7 pm and ending at 10 pm, but from earlier events it was evident that the sky was already quite dark by 6 pm, making a later setup difficult, so a 6 pm start for a Dark Stargaze seemed more appropriate than 7 pm.) Accordingly we four ORION astronomers arrived near 6 pm and began setting up, Art and David using their Seestars, and Rob and Ted using the Meade LX200.

Sunset	5:25 pm
Civ dusk	5:54 pm
Ast dusk	6:57 pm
Moonrise	12:35 pm
Moonset	11:54 pm
Moon illum.	42%

Sat 07 Dec 2024

A lovely sky on the chilly looking (and feeling) arrival and initial unpacking at TAO, taken at 6:18 pm Eastern, Sat 07 Dec 2024. Actually the temperature had only fallen to 35F by midnight, so this Stargaze was not nearly as cold as the previous two nights.

Public / Dark Stargaze & Continued Work on the Meade LX200

Sat 07 Dec 2024

I (Ted) had two goals for the evening. The most important to me was to try to understand how to adjust both Altitude (Alt) and Azimuth (Azi) using the fine adjustment screws on top of the main body of the mount. As I discussed last month, one could not complete CPWI's All Star Polar Alignment (ASPA) without being able to hand-adjust the mount's Alt and Azi axes. Unfortunately, the online Celestron CGE mount manual is rather sketchy in their discussion of these controls, and the crucial Fig.2-10 in the manual does not label the essential components (there are both Alt and Azi adjustment bolts and lock knobs, but only the Alt bolt and the Azi lock knobs are identified. I wanted to test my guesses as to the identities of the two unlabeled components, the *Azi adjustment bolt* and the *Alt lock knobs*. As a reminder, Fig.2-10 is reproduced below, from the earlier discussion of the 26 Nov Stargaze.

To adjust the mount in altitude:

1. Locate the altitude adjustment bolt just above the tripod column (see figure 2-10).
2. Using the 7/32" Allen wrench provided, turn the altitude adjustment bolt until the mount is at the right elevation.

The total altitude range is from 13° to 65°. With the 23 lb counterweight attached to the counterweight shaft, the equatorial head can go as low as 20° without hitting the tripod leg.

To adjust the mount in azimuth:

Fig.2-10 (not labeled in manual)

1. Locate the azimuth adjustment bolt on the flat portion of the tripod column (see figure 2-10).
2. Loosen the two azimuth lock knobs located on the top of the tripod column.
3. Turn the azimuth adjustment bolt with the 7/32" Allen wrench until the polar axis is pointing in the right direction.
4. Tighten the azimuth lock knobs to hold the mount in place. The mount can be moved $\pm 7^\circ$ in azimuth using these bolts.

My second goal for the evening was to capture an image of a probably near maximum light supernova, the type Ia 2024abuh in Pegasus, now at mag 15.2. This sounded like a nice Meade LX200 activity.

Public / Dark Stargaze & Continued Work on the Meade LX200

Sat 07 Dec 2024

Both of these activities obviously required alignment, so I set up my Win10 CPU “Sapphire,” Rob opened up the Meade dome, inserted the Celestron Wifi dongle, powered up the CGE mount, and attached my ZWO ASI294MCP camera to the base of the Meade. I turned on CPWI and SharpCap, connected to both TAO and CGE Wifi networks, and began an HC-free alignment. I used “Last Align” on CPWI since that previous 26 Nov star pointing set data had been saved, and did a sync on Kochab. This was a bit slow since the camera was initially way out of focus, so I started with a very large, off-center Airy disk, and Rob gradually improved the focus and I followed it’s position, and recentered Kochab.

About this time, *ca.* 8:00 pm, a car appeared, and parked in front of the N-most shed, giving us considerable light from bright headlights. Who might this be? No other ORION astronomers were expected, and David had sent out a cancellation notice for the Public Stargaze. However I had wondered if everyone had seen the cancellation, and despite the cold weather, I speculated that we might still see a few visitors at TAO who had missed seeing the notice. That was indeed the situation; these were people from a local church group who had decided to visit us. After David had met them I came up to say hello, and they were very interested to see the Meade inside the dome, and the terminals and programs I had set up and was running to control the telescope. I fielded a large number of questions from this interested and intelligent group, and demonstrated using the CPU to control the pointing direction of the OTA, and they enjoyed seeing the green laser tracing a slew between stars, in this case from Kochab to Deneb. They were quite impressed by the CPWI screen showing all the constellations and indicating the current OTA position. They were also enthusiastic to see various objects in the sky.

Fortunately Rob helped out by setting up the Meade on wheels, and was quickly able to show them views of the crescent Moon, as well as Saturn and

Public / Dark Stargaze & Continued Work on the Meade LX200

Sat 07 Dec 2024

Jupiter. I was having trouble getting a reliable signal from my camera through two coupled USB3.0 cables (just as 2 weeks previously), so I was unfortunately unable to show our visitors a nice live image of Jupiter through the Meade LX200, as I had hoped. An image of our visitors queueing to see the Moon, Jupiter and Saturn at Rob's portable Meade is shown below.

Public Stargaze visitors queueing for a view of the Moon, Saturn and Jupiter through the portable Meade operated by Rob Fowler.
8:08 pm Eastern, Sat 07 Dec 2024 at TAO.

As time passed, additional visitors from the same group arrived, I think there were four carloads, all very interested to see what we were doing, and to ask what was currently visible in the sky. After they had their tour, we discussed their interests with several who remained until about 10 pm; we promised to send them more information, and encouraged future return visits.

Public / Dark Stargaze & Continued Work on the Meade LX200

Sat 07 Dec 2024

Having an unexpected Public Stargaze with a moderately large group on this cold, dark night was an enjoyable and unexpected surprise for all four of us ORION members. (We talked about their visit for some time afterwards.)

After our visitors left I returned to the Meade LX200 and my connectivity problems, and of course it worked quite quickly and gave me just the sort of image of Jupiter and the Galilean moons I had been hoping to show our visitors. An example is shown below.

A view of Jupiter and the four Galilean Moons, taken using the Meade LX200 soon after most of our Public Stargaze visitors had departed. 9:30 pm Eastern, Sat 07 Dec 2024 at TAO.

My original “Astronomy” task for the Meade LX200 that night had been to capture an image of the moderately bright supernova 2024abuh, a type Ia that had recently been reported in galaxy UGC 12763 in Pegasus. Since everything was still aligned I slewed to the relevant field, not far from Algenib in Pegasus,

Public / Dark Stargaze & Continued Work on the Meade LX200

Sat 07 Dec 2024

and captured a few single-frame test images. They looked rather similar to the field sketch I had prepared earlier, but I couldn't find an exact agreement, and anyway the camera angle was unknown, so I decided to take a longer stack of that field and hope for the best. In the event I was fortunate, and the field I captured did include the mag 15.2 supernova. A cropped image with post-processing for enhanced color and color contrast is shown below.

Supernova 2024abuh (at center), discovered on 20 Nov 2024, now mag 15.2, a type Ia in Pegasus, in spiral (Sd) galaxy UGC 12763, distance *ca.* 210 Mly. This is a square crop (1573 px sq., just below 8' sq.) of a stack of 120 8-sec frames at the camera's maximum gain of 570, 120x8sG570, capture midpt 10:18 pm Eastern, 7 Dec 2024, at TAO. The faintest stars just visible here are 19th mag.

Public / Dark Stargaze & Continued Work on the Meade LX200

Sat 07 Dec 2024

The plate solver found that the raw image had a camera angle of $\theta_{\text{Cam}} = 93.96^\circ$, so for the image shown above I simply rotated the original image by 90° .

My final goal for the evening, for which I asked Rob and Art to remain for another half hour of deepening cold, was to try to identify the Azi adjustment bolt and Alt lock screws on the CGE mount. I had just slewed to Mars and captured a series of 1200 frames as an Avi file to try to stack later, so the laser on the OTA was already in position to use Mars as a reference target. The relevant region of the GCE mount is shown again on the following page.

First, the Alt adjustment bolt is visible as a black disk mounted vertically on the lower RHS of the vertical semicircular metal block, near the base. This bolt takes a $3/16''$ Allen key, not $7/32''$ as stated in the CGE manual. However attempting to adjust the Alt bolt had little effect on the laser beam's position. The screws mounted on each side of this Alt bolt also accepted a $3/16''$ Allen key, and when I loosened them I found that the Alt bolt now turned easily, and actually did change the OTA's Alt setting! So those two horizontal screws actually ARE the mount's Azi lock screws. This solved half of the problem with Alt / Azi mount settings. (Actually I discovered the Alt lock screws last, when we were finally returning the mount to Home.)

The second problem was to identify the fine manual Azi adjustment. (The Azi locks are little winged knobs on the horizontal part of the mount, turned by hand, which were clearly identified in the manual.) The obvious guess was a bolt near a winged Azi lock knob, mounted into the horizontal surface and going downwards into the mount. (See figure following page.) This bolt also accepted a $3/16''$ Allen key, but seemed loose and had no effect on the OTA's azimuth, even when the winged Azi lock knobs were loosened. Perhaps the Azi bolt's threads had been stripped during the many years of service? Although this possible Azi adjustment bolt had no effect, I accidentally discovered that

when the Azi winged lock knobs were loosened, the azimuth of the OTA could easily be changed by moving the large grey metal arm (labeled Azi arm below) horizontally. Small changes in the OTA's Azi to the left resulted from light taps to the right at point A1, and Azi changes to the right followed from light taps to the left on the opposite surface of the arm. When the desired Azi is reached, one simply retightens the Azi lock knobs.

The top of the CGE mount, showing the now understood Alt adjustment system, and the partly understood Azi adjustments, with a workaround that allows Azi adjustments to be implemented.

With these discoveries my weeks of not understanding how to make Alt and Azi fine adjustments by hand on the CGE mount were at an end. All rejoice! We next returned the mount to a suitable Home Position, shut TAO down, and departed about midnight from this very successful Stargaze.

**Mar 2025 Trapezium
Cover**

ORION | Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

The venerable Meade LX200 at TAO, opened for cleaning and refurbishment on the evening of Mon 03 Mar 2025, under Drew Bolci's expert supervision. Problems addressed included repairing a focus knob that was slipping and needed new hardware, and cleaning the corrector plate and secondary mirror. The baffle tube is visible below, set into the primary mirror. Unfortunately we could not identify the cause of the "bite" in the Airy disk noted previously in the Trapezium, see for example p.34 of the Dec 2024 issue. A follow-up Airy disk test on 12 Mar 2025 showed that this problem remains. We thank Noah Frere and his RSCC astronomy class for sharing their time, space, and facilities for this important and impromptu event.

Apr 2025 Trapezium
pp.47-50, 53-60

Surprise Dark Stargaze of

Tue 01 Apr 2025

Occasionally we have a nearly spontaneous Dark Stargaze event at TAO mainly for the ORION Staff, for example when a clear sky is predicted, and the day has been a beautiful eggshell blue, often the day after a heavy rainstorm. Since we have our weekly ORION Board Meeting on Mondays at the ElCantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge, a clear sky can motivate a trip to TAO that night or perhaps the following night, depending on local events and the predicted weather.

Tue 01 Apr 2025

Sunset	8:02 pm
Civ dusk	8:27 pm
Ast dusk	9:29 pm
Moonrise	9:13 am
Moonset*	12:25 am
	* 2 Apr

Moon illum. 13%

This was one such event. At the Monday lunch we agreed that Tuesday, April Fool's Day, had a nice sky predicted, so that would be a Dark Stargaze, with arrival at the TAO gate planned for 7:00 pm.

Crescent Moon during this event.

ORION President Don Spong setting up in the unaccustomed luxury of the new 20 ft sq concrete pad at TAO, 7:42 pm Eastern, 1 Apr 2025. This is the new pad's first astronomical activity. Note misleading blue sky.

Surprise Dark Stargaze (cont.)

Three of us, Art, Rob and Ted, were early enthusiastic arrivals at TAO gate on Tues 01 April 2025, and were all there by 6:40 pm. David arrived about 7:15 pm, and Don soon afterwards, so we had a group of 5 senior astronomers plus Sunny the Astrodog.

Perhaps not surprisingly for April Fool's Day, the weather quickly deteriorated from a mostly clear sky to a misty low haze with few stars visible. It did clear afterwards, first in regions (see below), then by 11 pm to a surprisingly clear sky almost everywhere. But by then we were discouraged, and all departed soon before midnight.

Rob aligning the Meade LX200 on Sirius from within the glowdome, 9:54 pm. Left and below Canis Major one can see deep Southern stars in Puppis, including the famous O5Ia supergiant Naos (ζ Pup) at -40.0° Dec, just above the center of the dome. Up and left from Naos one can even see two stars in the underappreciated constellation Pyxis.

Surprise Dark Stargaze (cont.)

I had brought some art supplies to the event, and chopped an annular filter out of stiff black cardboard for the Meade LX200, hoping to block the optical anomaly that is visible as a bite in the Airy disk. (Filter radius dimensions 4.5" I.D., 6.5" O.D.) Perhaps surprisingly this filter fit nicely in the front of the OTA, see image below. Airy disks showed that it did succeed in blocking the optical anomaly. Images of "before" and "after" Airy disks of Betelgeuse are shown on the page following. Although the filter was successful, and it did removed scattered light from star images, the reduced aperture lost just over a magnitude in image brightness. We still hope to identify and correct the actual optical problem in the front of the OTA, whatever it is.

Surprise Dark Stargaze (cont.)

Airy disks of Betelgeuse, taken without (above) and with (below) the optical filter in place. Clearly the optical defect has been blocked, but at the cost of a factor of about 2.5 in light gathering power. Corresponding enlarged star images at focus without and with the filter in place (above and below respectively) are shown at right. One could increase the filter I.D. to 5.0" and recover some of the reduced aperture without losing the improved Airy disk and tighter star image. Perhaps next time?

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse of 14 Mar.

- Ted Barnes

This story is a little complicated as it covers two topics on two disjoint days, developments regarding repair and refurbishment of the Meade LX200, on both 11 and 14 Mar 2025, *and* the observation and recording of the Total Lunar Eclipse at TAO on 14 Mar 2025. So, let's start at the beginning, with our initial pre-eclipse trip to TAO on Tue 11 Mar 2025.

i) 11 Mar 2025

David, Rob and I decided that there was sufficient motivation for a special trip to TAO on that date. First, I wanted to measure the Morrow-scope, since we had discussed looking for a dome for this telescope repeatedly, but no one had quite gotten around to measuring the scope when fully assembled. So we did that. The results are a separation between tripod leg end points (at bottom) of 35 in; a vertical distance from the floor to the platform the mount rests on of 38 in; the height of the scope from the floor to the highest point on the OTA, maybe a few inches less than 95 in (call it 8 ft to be cautious); the (intermediate) height of the scope from the floor to the top of the mounting plate for the OTA, 68 in.

Personally I might recommend that a dome provide at least 2 ft of clearance above the top of the OTA. Thus the dome interior ceiling level should be at least 10 ft. Rob and David agreed this was higher than they had expected.

Next we proceeded to work on the LX200 OTA. The names used may be a little confusing, since this Meade LX200 telescope sits atop a Celestron mount, of the venerable model CGE. Initially for fun I used AnyDesk to contact my home office computer at 9:07 pm, and instructed it to play some music for Agatha's benefit. This probably worked, and if so it was a record distance AnyDesk session for us of about 40 km, but Agatha was apparently asleep, and missed hearing the music. In the interim Rob set up his PC connection to the CGE through a wifi dongle, and aligned the LX200 using Caph, Alioth, Sirius and Rigel, using one of my ZWO ASI294MCP cameras. No one had brought binoculars (oops), so the alignment by eyeball of laser beam and stars was probably less accurate than one might have expected. I confirmed that a long USB3.0 cable I had purchased some time ago but never unwrapped (10 ft length I think) worked well for this exercise. I also used AnyDesk to connect my PC to Rob's, so some of the subsequent effort used both pcs.

We had hoped to use the Plate Solver on SharpCap to orient the Meade's camera to North by plate solving a star field, since SC displays a current camera angle with respect to N after plate solving. Alas Rob's two versions of SharpCap didn't have this recent Plate Solver function, so he had to resubscribe to SharpCap Pro and dnload the latest version. Although this dnload worked, we were still unable to successfully solve Meade star fields. SharpCap seemed to want more stars to solve the field than the ~ 20 to 56 it identified.

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse.

(cont.)

Here are two nice images of Rob (inside the dome) aligning the LX200 OTA on two bright stars to the South in Canis Major and Orion, using the scope control program CPWI and the LX200's newish laser pointer. The stars are of course Sirius (L) and Rigel (R) .

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse. (cont.)

Rob DID confirm on 11 Mar that the previous repair of the Meade LX200 focus knob on 03 Mar 2025 had not corrected the Airy disk problem. Two Airy disks that he captured on 11 Mar are shown below. The one at left looks very similar to our previous LX200 Airy disk images, and the one at right looks like the “cusp” disk we saw through an eyepiece after the LX200 repair effort of 03 Mar. This image at right is presumably the “left” Airy disk when viewed on the other side of the focal plane.

This speculation needs to be confirmed, as the two images were captured quickly late in the evening. The one at left, very similar in appearance to our earlier Airy disks, confirmed our suspicion that the optical flaw that produced the strange Airy disk had not been affected by the LX200 repair effort.

So, we departed TAO at about 11:30 pm, having confirmed to our satisfaction that the Airy disk problem remained unsolved..

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse. (cont.)

Now we proceed to 14 Mar 2025, including the observation of the Total Lunar Eclipse at TAO *and* further adventures with the LX200 on the same date. Let's start with our plans for viewing the Total Lunar Eclipse on 14 Mar 2025.

ii) 13-14 Mar 2025

Our chatter on WhatsApp regarding what we should do for the total lunar eclipse, the only one of 2025, only started seriously when it was already Thursday 13 Mar, the day immediately before eclipse night. People seemed to have conflicts (Noah and Rob), or just some kind of burnout from several recent and coming events. I said that I thought we really had to show up at TAO for an important event like this, and attempt some astrophotography. We could use the Meade, so equipment transport was not a problem. I suggested meeting around sunset. Art just wanted to know when to turn up. Apparently Juan said that he could just step outside to see the eclipse, so he saw no need to travel to TAO. David said that he had had a very long day and needed to rest before this very late event. According to the summary I found at Nasa's GSFC site <https://eclipse.gsfc.nasa.gov/eclipse.html>, although Penumbral contact started at 11:57 pm Eastern on 13 Mar, the deepest (Umbral) part of the eclipse lasted from 2:26 - 3:31 am Eastern, 14 Mar. Thus treating the eclipse with proper respect would require staying until at least 4 am. (In the event I actually left TAO at 4:38 am, 14 Mar 2025, so to my mind the Moon was adequately celebrated.)

David suggested that we arrive at TAO about 11 pm, which I thought was fine for this event. Art was still “Go.” I arrived at the gate of deep dark TAO about 10:45 pm, and Art was already there. David arrived soon after, and we began setting up. Here we see David and Art in the TAO classroom, waiting for the eclipse to intensify. Image time 1:29 am Eastern, about an hour before totality. David and Art had both brought Moon-related edibles.

Total Lunar Eclipse of 2025 Mar 14

Ecliptic Conjunction = 06:55:48.0 TD (= 06:54:33.5 UT)

Greatest Eclipse = 06:59:56.2 TD (= 06:58:41.7 UT)

Penumbral Magnitude = 2.2595 P. Radius = 1.1899° Gamma = 0.3484
 Umbral Magnitude = 1.1784 U. Radius = 0.6537° Axis = 0.3171°

Saros Series = 123 Member = 53 of 73

Sun at Greatest Eclipse
(Geocentric Coordinates)

R.A. = 23h37m46.0s
 Dec. = -02°24'16.8"
 S.D. = 00°16'05.2"
 H.P. = 00°00'08.8"

Moon at Greatest Eclipse
(Geocentric Coordinates)

R.A. = 11h38m23.0s
 Dec. = +02°40'54.6"
 S.D. = 00°14'52.8"
 H.P. = 00°54'36.8"

Eclipse Durations

Penumbral = 06h02m37s
 Umbral = 03h38m15s
 Total = 01h05m24s

ΔT = 75 s

Rule = CdT (Danjon)

Eph. = VSOP87/ELP2000-85

Eclipse Contacts

P1 = 03:57:24 UT
 U1 = 05:09:33 UT
 U2 = 06:25:59 UT
 U3 = 07:31:23 UT
 U4 = 08:47:48 UT
 P4 = 10:00:01 UT

F. Espenak, NASA's GSFC
eclipse.gsfc.nasa.gov/eclipse.html

A detailed chart of UT times of various aspects of the 14 Mar 2025 Total Lunar Eclipse. This is c/o NASA, as cited. Eastern times are UT - 4 hrs.

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse. (cont.)

Initially David wanted to stare into the Meade, to see if he could identify the defect responsible for the flawed Airy disk. (We had noticed earlier that the Airy disk problem had not been solved by Drew's earlier successful repair of the focus knob; the Airy disk only looked different on the 2 sides of the focal plane, corresponding to different focuser settings. One side still had the familiar dark edge "bite" that we had first observed months before; see the preceding notes in this article for 11 Mar 2025.) David wanted to try to clarify the location of the flaw, specifically its " ϕ " angle around the OTA. By holding up a yardstick while David watched the Airy disk through an eyepiece, we were able to identify the location as being just below the text "Meade LX200 EMC" on the exterior of the OTA, near a small white hand-drawn x just below the forward end of the OTA. There is a small dark grey annular gasket that sits just inside the front corrector plate on the Meade, and when it was opened inside the TAO classroom on 3 Mar 2025, it was evident that a short section was missing from this gasket. David suggested that this gasket anomaly might be the cause of the irregular Airy disk, as it appeared to be at about the same angle ϕ on the OTA. A very compelling suggestion! This can be easily tested by placing a small piece of black material of the same shape as the missing gasket section on the front of the OTA; does this repair the Airy disk? An important future next step in this long saga. It would also be interesting to prepare several OTA cutout masks of black construction paper to test their results on the Airy disk.

This shows the OTA with the glass corrector plate removed, in the TAO classroom on 3 Mar 2025. The gap in the annular gasket, which may be the origin of the irregularity in the Airy disk noted previously, is indicated by the red arrow.

Location of the gap in the annular gasket.

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse. (cont.)

This was very important, but we were after all present at TAO because of the lunar eclipse, and I was interested in getting the Meade to point at the Moon in the very near future. We had actually started the “bootup” procedure with the Meade earlier, at 10:20 pm Eastern, for this reason. I had brought two Celestron wifi dongles for the mount, and David used the first, in the aux1 socket. My PC “Sapphire,” a Win10 box, showed both the Celestron-C1F and observatory wifi signals, which connected to my pc’s wifi and wifi2 networks respectively.

I initially started CPWI with the wrong coordinates (Clinton, LRO, instead of TAO), so in the CPWI Alignment function I fixed this, and used Load Alignment to load a 10-star TAO pointing model from 28 Jan 2025 (the only one I had that was marked TAO; there were about a dozen from LRO).

Quite early on, during a slew to Kochab, my PC lost contact with the mount, so I repeated the entire procedure. A move to Alkaid was successful (this was one of CPWI’s suggested sync stars), but again the wifi connection to the mount was lost. Very frustrating! Removing the “observatory” wifi connection from my PC didn’t solve the problem.

I returned the mount to Home (always a bit up and left of Polaris, reached repeatedly that evening), and this time I simply tried to slew to the Moon by hand using the CPWI slew control. Alas the gremlins continued to appear, and one of the compass directions in the CPWI slew control seemed to have a problem. The slew control would simply not advance in that direction! This was starting to sound like Apollo 13. Finally I asked David to just release the clutches and point the OTA at the Moon by hand. (The laser pointer at least was working.) Once at the Moon, with the tracking speed set to Lunar, all was strangely ok, all compass directions worked in the CPWI slew control, but one direction was much slower than the others. [Later I saw that CPWI listed a Dec of 89.6 deg in my images, so the problem was an incorrect and almost singular assumed location in polar coordinates. Bizarre.]

Anyway, I was now able to take many LX200 pictures of the Moon with my ASI294MCP camera attached, with a reasonably good focus, but with a strange slightly purple cast, not the deep red most lunar eclipse astrophotographers seem to encounter. Some examples are shown in the Astrophotography section, after post-processing to dilute the purple cast. Meanwhile Art had been using his Seestar 50 to capture lunar eclipse images, and these are much more satisfying; see cover, as well as the Astrophotography section.

Meade LX200 Adventures and the Lunar Eclipse. (cont.)

After we passed the end of the Umbral (total) stage of the eclipse, at 3:31 am Eastern, things grew rather more relaxed. My collection of Moon Music was aired in part. I recalled a small illuminated lunar globe that I had brought but had forgotten to set up, and took a few images of that for fun, one of which appears on p.3. Another is shown below.

The glow-dome, Meade LX200, and my setup for controlling the Meade and Celestron mount with CPWI and SharpCap; image capture at 4:05 am Eastern, 14 Mar 2025. The Moonglobe could obviously be used for some amusing photographic effects. Maybe next year. I left TAO about 4:38 am, and finally reached home about 5:40 am.

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Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

The high point for astroimaging in Mar 2025 was the total lunar eclipse of Fri 14 Mar 2025 (incidentally also “ π day”). In our case we gathered three ORION astronomers at the last moment for a Moongaze at TAO, starting at 11 pm and ending around 4:30 am, and made an effort to capture images of the Total Lunar Eclipse early in the morning of 14 Mar, using the Meade LX200 and Art’s Seestar 50. Organizational aspects of this trip appear in the preceding article. Some of those lunar images appear here, as well as a few contributed by ORION members from outside TAO.

(L to R) Ted Barnes, Art Allison and David Fields in the TAO building, preparing for a night of total lunar eclipse.

Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

Ted Barnes

Ted used the Meade LX200 with a ZWO ASI294MCP camera attached, the mount operated by CPWI, and using SharpCap Pro to display and capture images. This is a cellphone image of the SCPro display, taken at 1:26 am, during the Penumbral stage of the eclipse. This is a live display of full-field (4144x2822 px), 0.25 ms images, with a camera gain of 400. The two large mare in the upper part of the image are (L to R) Mare Serenitatis and Mare Tranquillitatis. This image was post-processed for sharpness and contrast. A suggestion of a faint reddish tint in the lunar image is evident here.

Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

Ted's raw images during the Umbral phase somehow acquired a purple tint, which was largely suppressed in post-processing. Two examples of these images are shown here and on the following page. These Umbral phase images required a much longer exposure; this one was 1/15 sec at a gain of 514, taken at 2:41:44 am Eastern.

This shows the NE region of the Moon, with Mare Crisium near top right, and below it from L to R are the large Mare Serenitatis, Tranquillitatis, and Fecunditatis.

Total Lunar Eclipse Images from 14 Mar 2025.

(TAO and elsewhere).

In this image the large crater at lower left is Copernicus, adjacent to Mare Imbrium. This image was captured at 3:01:22 am Eastern, in the Umbral phase just after greatest eclipse. It used a 1/30 sec exposure with a gain of 570 (maximum) and was post-processed, primarily for increased contrast and to suppress a purple tint.

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pp.46-50

Work continues on the TAO Meade LX-200 telescope.

Stage 1 (OTA) was cleaning of lens surfaces. Thanks, everyone.

Stage 2 was to improve the images by identifying and cleaning up errors (made obvious by examining the Fresnel diffraction patterns of stars – see photo below). Thanks Ted, Rob and David.

Stage 3 (mount hardware upgrades) was identifying and replacing faulty microswitches in the Meade hardware home reference system (Celestron CGX mount).

Stage 4 was cleaning and greasing the gears and some bearings. Thanks, George and David.

Stage 5 (testing) showed that earlier work looked ok, and that there was no loss of RA reference by running the scope from side to side. Thanks, Rob and Kevin.

Stage 6 will be to identify occasional glitches in slewing. Possible causes include incompatible setup of clocks set to EST and EDT in different modules (Celestron mount, control computers using different programs (Celestron, Stellarium, Sky Safari, etc., and GPS); need to replace Li-ion cells in Celestron mount). Rob and David have discussed this. Stage 7 is to explore questions related to electrical noise generated by the switching supply and the effects of the noise on the tracking system (Celestron CGE mount). The approach will be to measure noise and examine if it is associated with a power supply with a low

current rating, or with switching noise harmonics. If a problem for the telescope or nearby system components using Bt or WiFi, we'll install ferrite suppressors. This topic is especially relevant if we want to do radio astronomy from TAO, as we have done several times in the past. More detailed discussion:

On Saturday, May 24, 2025 at 06:36:38 PM EDT, David Fields <fieldsde@aol.com> wrote:

Notes by George and David on 5/24/2025:

The mount is currently served by a (probably inadequate) Celestron 2A power supply. A 5A supply should be ordered -- I will do this. I am delighted that George noticed that we need a power supply rated for a higher current. I will also rig up a current/voltage monitor system to see how close we are to the rated limits with the current supply. We should not just worry just about driving the scope, but we should recognize that the switching power supplies are likely to generate electrical interference when they are overloaded. This may explain some of our glitches during Wi-Fi and bte operation. Before we put the new 5A supply in operation, I will follow George's suggestion and put a few turns of the DC line through a ferrite doughnut to absorb the Rf switching noise.

We serviced the RA electronics section of the CGE mount, resoldering some possible cold solder joints and replacing two micro switches. Also, the RA gear train (worm gear?) was lubed. We exercised the mount and insured that it passes some basic operational tests.

The mount is still in need of receiving lubrication for the Dec worm gear and inspection of the Dec electronics.

Proper operation of the mount depends on proper balancing. We left the system balanced for visual monitoring. It will need to be rebalanced when/if a camera is used.

The new microswitches that we added to the RA mechanics have plastic rollers, which may deform if left in the same position for many hot days. The new switches will probably work for years, but we have no real assurance of their lifetime.

We left the two old microswitches plus one additional new microswitch, in a plastic bag stuffed under a flat plate below the mount. We will add these to the lens box in the dome.

On Sunday, May 25, 2025 at 01:39:56 AM EDT, Djerdj Srdanov <sdjerdj@yahoo.com> wrote:

Thank you David for the detailed notes. Here are a few more details:

After inspecting the PCBs under high magnification, I've found a few solder points that looked as cracked or a bit oxidized. (Images are available.) To be safe, I've re-soldered all of the pins on the 2 PCBs in the RA box.

With that out of the way, the switches were next. Swapping out the switches was straightforward. However, during testing, I noticed that the top switch was bumping into the groove of the lower one. This new problem popped up on multiple threads during my research to find a match for the switches on the mount. I've run across multiple threads dealing with similar problems, as well as dealing with slightly thinner switches. To get the switch off the edge of the groove, we made a small shim and placed it between the 2 switches. Both the shim and the new clearly visible gap are marked in the attached pictures (images available). After adding the shim and adjusting the level of the switches, we got ourselves a nice "click" sound when the switches engage or disengage. We also noticed that the new switches are more firm and require a bit more force to engage. I don't think this will be an issue; perhaps this is how a new switch feels.

Finally, during testing I've observed that the mount behaved slightly different depending on where it pointed. For some reason, this became more obvious when I applied fresh silicon grease to the gears at the end of the motor, as well as to the worm gear. When I checked the power source, I noticed that it is only 2A. For a small mount 2A should be fine, but for something as big as this one, with the big Meade LX-200 mounted on it, I feel this is undersized. I've also observed over the years that if a power supply is pushed to its maximum ratings, it can produce noisy power. I highly recommend we get a 5A power supply. If of a decent quality, it should provide better stability, and produce cleaner power.

This is what I have been using with my EQ-6 - This power supply lets me run the EQ6, the dew heaters and the camera with the cooler on; [https:// www dot amazon dot com/ dp/ B01LX5LRP9](https://www.amazon.com/dp/B01LX5LRP9) .

Ahh, yes. Before I forget. The switches we have now are for normal temperature ranges, with plastic rollers. With the mount being in the dome, the temperature can be pretty high. This could cause the plastics rollers to potentially degrade or deform sooner. Since these are brand new, I don't foresee any issues any time soon, however if we need to replace them, I recommend we use the extended temperature range ones, with metal rollers. I believe a Highly (?) switches ([https:// www. jameco. com/ Jameco/ Products/ ProdDS/ 159599.pdf](https://www.jameco.com/Jameco/Products/ProdDS/159599.pdf)) - the model I believe is SS0505A would match. Another alternative, if not a better one, would be SS5GL02-F from Omron ([https:// omronfs. omron. com/ en_US/ ecb/ products/p df/ en-ss.pdf](https://omronfs.omron.com/en_US/ecb/products/pdf/en-ss.pdf) - the 02 is for the steel roller).

All in all, I'm pretty happy with the work done. Please keep me posted how the mount behaves.

Best regards,
George

n.b. The Editor made some minor, largely grammatical changes in the “Shop Talk” article where they appeared appropriate. The occasional remaining uncertainties are indicated by question marks.

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*Au Revoir et
Bonne Chance!*

